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Deliverable D8.4

FarFish final report

30/03/2022

Executive summary

This report provides an overall review of the FarFish project regarding project progress and main results. The project started in June 2017 and came to an end in November 2021. The main objective of the project was to “improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability”. Looking back on what the project has delivered it is safe to say that it has made significant contributions towards its main objective.

The FarFish project has now come to an end, after 4 ½ years of intensive research and innovation involving close to 200 scientists and stakeholders from across the world. Multidisciplinary team of experts from research, academia, governance & policy, fishing industry and NGO sectors have collaborated to contribute to more sustainable and profitable fisheries in long-distance waters. The aim of this report is to give an overview of the work done within the project and present the main results.

FarFish is funded by the EU H2020 research and innovation programme and has the objective to improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability. The EU fleet operates in long-distance waters around the world, either in international waters or within the waters of coastal states that have allowed access to surplus stocks via bilateral agreements. A total of 21% of the EU fleets catches are as results caught in non-EU waters. The fisheries within these waters are however often poorly regulated, management decisions are sometimes based on limited knowledge and enforcement capabilities, compliance and trust between stakeholders tend to lack. The EU does at the same time expect the EU fleets to set an example for other fleets regarding sustainability and best practice.

FarFish addresses the challenges faced by the EU fleet in long-distance waters in a multidisciplinary and innovative way by focusing on six diverse case studies, four within the waters of African countries that have signed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) with the EU and two in international waters. The project has enabled stakeholders from five continents, reaching from China to Brazil, to cooperate towards a common goal of improving sustainability and contribute to a more profitable seafood industry in all corners of the world’s oceans.

FarFish is unique to most H2020 research and innovation projects with respect to geographical coverage. It has enabled researchers, policymakers, government representatives and other stakeholders with very different background and priorities to collaborate towards a common goal. Language and cultural barriers have been an intrinsic part of the project, which has made it challenging but also extremely rewarding. The Covid 19 pandemic did affect FarFish particularly hard, as stakeholder participation remains at the core of the project. The FarFish consortium does though feel that they have managed to make the best out of a difficult situation, proving results that will keep the legacy of FarFish alive for years to come.

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1 Introduction

The FarFish project has now come to an end, after 4 ½ years of intensive research and innovation involving close to 200 scientists and stakeholders from across the world. Multidisciplinary team of experts from research, academia, governance & policy, fishing industry and NGO sectors have collaborated to contribute to more sustainable and profitable fisheries in long-distance waters. The aim of this report is to give an overview of the work done within the project and present the main results.

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2 FarFish objectives

The overall objective of FarFish was to “**improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability**”. The project was funded within the Horizon 2020 topic SFS-21-2016-2017 - [Advancing basic biological knowledge and improving management tools for commercially important fish and other seafood species](#), and was designed to address the challenges and expected impacts identified in the topic. A set of specific objectives (SOs) were defined within the project to address the call and contribute to the overall objective. The SOs were then operationalised through work packages (WPs), tasks and deliverables. The SOs were as follows:

SO1) To advance knowledge and collate data related to biological characteristics of the main fish stocks in selected fisheries outside EU waters that are important for the EU fleet, and to evaluate the relevance and applicability of appropriate stock assessment methods for these fisheries.

SO2) To map and analyse the value chains of the selected fisheries and their current infrastructure and to suggest improvements that promote future sustainability, profitability and predictable provision of seafood.

SO3) To analyse current legal and contractual practices and constraints in these fisheries, and to produce policy recommendations for improved management of these fisheries based on increased accountability and participation of resource users, including what the rights and obligations all parties involved should be.

SO4) To develop flexible, dynamic and ready-to-use Management Recommendations (MRs) in close collaboration with stakeholders based on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles for the selected fisheries, containing measures for approaching MSY levels.

SO5) To evaluate the relevance, applicability, sustainability, costs, benefits and compliance with overall goals for the MPs, and to provide feedback on feasibility and a roadmap for potential implementation.

SO6) To develop general fisheries management- and other decision support tools (DST). Provide recommendations relating to data sampling, stock assessment methods and management procedures, including when data availability is poor, and degree of control and enforcement is low.

SO7) To provide education, training and dissemination to stakeholders within the value chains of EU fisheries in SFPAs waters and international waters, and to improve their professional skills and regional networks.

3 Project structure and methodologies

FarFish was split up into seven work packages (WPs) that together contributed to reaching the overall objective.

WP1 - Stakeholder interaction (lead by CETMAR) focused on involving stakeholders in creating solutions, and bringing together the resources and competences of different stakeholders to support project partners to reach their objectives.

WP2 - Advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models (lead by CCMAR) related to SO1 and focused on the biological and ecological status of resources within the FarFish case studies (CSs). The scope of the WP included analysing the current status of relevant stocks and the ecosystems they live in, as well as investigating how stock assessments are being conducted, what data is available, how it is gathered and what models/tools are used for setting TACs. It was also to advance biological and ecological knowledge in the CSs.

WP3 - Value chain analysis, evaluation of existing governance structure and policy recommendations (lead by NOFIMA) related to SO2 and SO3, focusing on analysing the CS value chains from economic, social and legal point of view. Key socio-economic indicators were analysed, as well as logistics, production processes, products, labour and markets. The available infrastructure in the CS countries was as well analysed, along with the fisheries management Acts and overall management objectives in the relevant coastal states, SFPA agreements, CFP and RFMO mandates. For each CS the WP, in cooperation with the relevant authorities, designed and operationalised a results-based management (RBM) approach for the CSs, including identification of key objectives, Outcome Targets (OTs), associated indicators, and production of general guidelines for making MRs within the RBM process.

WP4 - Development of management plans (lead by UiT) related to SO4 and developed flexible, dynamic and ready-to-use MRs in close collaboration with stakeholders in each CS, following the general guidelines provided by WP3.

WP5 - Evaluation and implementation of management plans (lead by SYN/SJOKOVIN) related to So5 and performed “audits” on the MRs developed for each CS in WP4. The audit results were sent to the “authority” in WP3 and the “operators” in WP4, creating basis for improving the general guidelines for making MRs, the MR Invitations and the MRs. WP5 did also suggest improvements to challenges identified in the value chain mapping in WP3 and performed a cost-benefit analysis on potential investment opportunities for the EU fleet in SFPA countries. WP5 did as well provide policy recommendations for implementation of RBM in EU long-Distance fisheries.

WP6 – Development of management tools (lead by CSIC) related to SO6 by analysing the applicability of stock assessment models applied in the CSs and by developing new tools and methods for fisheries management in the CSs. The tools were aimed to suit data and technical competence within each CS, and ranged from simple statistical analysis to highly demanding approaches. The WP developed Decision Support and visualisation tools, which operate on free-platforms to facilitate actor interoperability, immediate implementation and sustainability beyond FarFish.

WP7 - Capacity building and dissemination (lead by GROFTP) related to SO7 and focused on improving professional skills and competences of stakeholders within the CSs and beyond within the field of fisheries management, as well as disseminating the project itself. The work included

education and knowledge transfer to a wide variety of stakeholders within the respective value chains, utilising solutions such as infomercials, social media, workshops, webinars, Tutor-web, etc. A special university-level certificate programme in Marine Management and Innovation was set-up for decision makers. The GROFTP organised a six-month programme tailor-made for FarFish, where people already working within the CS in influential positions received training and in-depth knowledge on fisheries management. The WP did also facilitate seven international conferences and workshops to disseminate project results and contribute to informed discussions on the project topics.

The WP interactions are shown in Figure 1, where the iterative process within the RBM approach in WP3-WP6 is highlighted.

Figure 1: The FarFish WPs and their interaction

FarFish addressed six strategically selected CSs that together provide a cross-section of SFPAs and high-seas fisheries that are important for the fishing fleets of multiple EU countries and respond to the priorities of RFMOs and the CFP. The CSs were selected based on a number of criteria. First of all, these areas all support fisheries that are relevant for the EU fleet and for supplying the European domestic market. This was a key criterion, as it means that any improvements in fisheries management and advanced knowledge FarFish produced in these areas will not only benefit the surrounding coastal states, but also the EU fleet, and thus encourage better participation from European scientists, managers and relevant stakeholders. Second, the understanding of the biology and ecology of many of the fish stocks of interest to the EU in these areas, and the overall ecosystem

effects of these fisheries, is far from complete, resulting in management decisions often being based on limited science. This can lead to overexploitation, with knock-on ecosystem, economic and social effects, both for the EU fleet and the coastal states. Third, management decisions, control measures and allocation of fishing opportunities in these areas are usually not negotiated with all relevant stakeholders, often resulting in a lack of compliance and enforcement. The CSs span from relatively simple single species fisheries (Cape Verde and Seychelles tuna fisheries), to a slightly more complicated multi species fisheries (Senegalese tuna and hake) to very complicated mixed fisheries (Mauritanian and the high seas mixed fisheries). By focusing on CSs of such a diverse nature, FarFish was able to get a holistic view of the main problems and limitations facing EU long-distance fleets. Together with scientists, stakeholders and policy makers, FarFish was able to advance knowledge of these fisheries and contribute to providing long-term, realistic and achievable solutions that can be applied to these fisheries, thus ensuring the long-term profitability of the EU long-distance fleet, market supply and a sustainable provision of seafood.

The case studies included two high-seas areas* and four areas where the EU has negotiated access for its long-distance fleets in Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs). As shown in Figure 2, The case studies were in the Southwest Atlantic international waters (FAO area 41), the Southeast Atlantic international waters (FAO area 47, SEAFO Convection Area), The Cape Verde SFPA fishery, the Senegal SFPA fishery, the Mauritania SFPA fishery and the Seychelles SFPA fishery.

Figure 2: The FarFish case studies

* The terms *high-seas*, *international waters* and *Areas Beyond National Jurisdictions (ABNJ)* are used in this document for all areas beyond national territorial waters.

The consortium gathered to carry out the project consisted of 21 partners from 12 countries. Seven (7) were marine research institutes, seven (7) research institutes, four (4) universities and three (3) representing the fishing industry. The partners were supported by a Reference Group, consisting of 21 stakeholders that provided input to the project, ranging from following the project as observers to taking active part in certain tasks. The FarFish consortium is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The FarFish consortium

The FarFish project was originally planned to last for four years but was extended by 6-months due to Covid 19. During that time the project produced 66 deliverables, which are shown in the following table.

Table 1: FarFish deliverables

Del. No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Month
D7.1	Project webpage	MATIS	1
D2.1	Case study characterization	CCMAR	3
D6.1	Data input protocol for the FFDB	MATIS	4
D2.2	Data Management Plan under the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot	NOFIMA	6
D7.2	Dissemination and exploitation plan	UNUFTP	6
D7.3	Tutor-web FarFish initial setup	MATIS	6
D9.1	POPD - Requirement No. 1	MATIS	7
D4.1	MPO for each case study	UiT	9
D3.1	Draft 1 general guidelines for making MPs	MATIS	10

D1.1	Executive report on stakeholder hub: attributes, tools and feedback	CETMAR	11
D3.2	First MP invitations submitted to case studies	MATIS	12
D6.2	FFDB pilot version 1	MATIS	12
D6.3	Visualisation materials and tools available for MP1 development	MATIS	12
D6.4	Report on developments needed to produce relevant management tools	CSIC	12
D7.4	Report on training needs assessment	UNUFTP	12
D2.3	Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 1	CCMAR	14
D4.2	Report from the MP Kick-off meetings	UiT	14
D8.1	First annual report	MATIS	14
D2.4	Templates and protocols for self-sampling	CCMAR	16
D3.3	Report on evaluation of governance structures of the cases	NOFIMA	16
D3.4	Report on description of value chains and input-output structure of the CS	NOFIMA	18
D4.3	MP1 for each CS	UiT	20
D2.5	Report on evaluation of current stock assessment models used in CS	CCMAR	24
D5.1	Report on the MP1 audit	SYN	24
D7.5	University-level diploma programme in Marine Management and Innovation launched	UiT	24
D7.6	Advanced post-graduate training program launched	UNUFTP	24
D7.7	Tutor-web educational material ready	MATIS	24
D1.2	Intermediate report on Stakeholder hub implementation: lessons learnt and improvement areas for second spiral interaction	CETMAR	26
D2.6	Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 2	CCMAR	26
D3.5	Draft 2 general guidelines for making MPs	MATIS	26
D3.6	Second MP invitation submitted to case studies	MATIS	26
D5.2	Report on challenges and suggestions for improvements	SYN	26
D6.5	FFDB pilot version 2	MATIS	26
D6.6	Visualisation materials and tools available for MP2 development	MATIS	26
D6.7	Report on DSTs used in CSs for developing MP1	CSIC	26
D8.2	Second annual report	MATIS	26
D1.3	Report on game theory and associated tools for improving fisheries agreements	CCMAR	35
D2.7	Report on the success of the self-sampling programme	CCMAR	36
D5.3	Report on potential return of investments	SYN	36
D6.8	Interactive Platform to integrate codes, visualization and data interaction tools for the selected CSs	CSIC	36
D8.3	Third annual report	MATIS	38
D6.9	FFDB	MATIS	40
D4.4	MR2 for each CS	UiT	42
D2.10	Report on the data collected on small pelagics and environmental forcing on the west coast of Africa	UCAM	43
D2.8	Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB	CCMAR	46
D5.4	Report on the MR2 audit	SJOKOVIN	46

D3.10	Review on how European fleet international- and SFPA water fisheries are managed and conducted	NOFIMA	47
D7.9	Report on University-level certificate programme in Marine Management and Innovation	UiT	47
D1.4	Policy Brief on the CFP external dimension towards 2022	CETMAR	50
D6.10	Report on the DSTs used in CSs for developing MR2	CSIC	50
D1.5	Summary report for the Workshop on “Improving management under fisheries agreements”	CETMAR	50
D3.8	Report on the governance of European fisheries in international- and SFPA waters	NOFIMA	50
D7.10	Report on the advanced post-graduate training program	GROFTP	50
D2.9	WP2 final report	CCMAR	52
D7.8	Report on Tutor-web training activities in FarFish	MATIS	52
D1.6	Measuring socio-economic impacts of the SFPA through the analysis of EU Fleet (inter) connections in foreign countries	CETMAR	52
D3.9	Report on the value chain analysis for EU fisheries in international- and SFPA waters	NOFIMA	52
D3.11	Policy recommendations relating to how European fleet international- and SFPA water fisheries could be managed and conducted	NOFIMA	52
D4.5	Report on “Implementing RFMS in international- and SFPA waters: lessons learned in pilot studies”	UiT	52
D5.5	Policy recommendations for improved management through the adoption of RFMS for EU vessels fishing in international- and SFPA waters	SJOKOVIN	52
D6.11	Report on small-pelagics and environmental forcing off the west coast of Africa	UCAM	52
D7.11	Report on the success of in-country workshop	GROFTP	52
D7.12	Project summary report aimed at a wider audience	MATIS	53
D3.7	General guidelines for making MRs published as CWA	MATIS	54
D7.13	Concluding symposium	GROFTP	54
D8.4	Final report	MATIS	54

The deliverables reported on the progress and main results, which were as follows:

Month 1 - The FarFish webpage

The FarFish Project website www.farfish.eu is the primary dissemination and communication platform of the project. The site gives project partners, stakeholders and the general public the opportunity to get information on the project and its progress. It also enables for easy linkage to social media. The content on the website is designed to be informative on main tasks in the project and to provide detailed information on the case studies, workshops, meetings and other activities, as well as progress. The website allows for those interested to sign up for a newsletter, which were

published regularly throughout the project lifetime. The FFDB (FarFish DataBase) is accessible through the webpage. The website does as well have an internal / restricted access component, where documents and data intended for internal use are stored. The internal website is divided into seven folders, each with separate restriction access. Project partners, selected stakeholders, reference group members and external advisors have been given access to these folders, as deemed appropriate by the website administration team. There is also a folder titled “restricted data” which only very selected few have access to. The website was developed by Matís, which is also responsible for its hosting and maintenance. Selected project partners have been given editorial rights to the site.

The website is set up in WordPress, which is simple and commonly used platform. The intention of Matís is to keep the page open for at least three years after the project end, at own cost, in order to facilitate that the project and its products will live on. The project webpage will be moved to the Matís domain after that time.

Month 3 – Case study characterisation

This report contained basic description of the six FarFish CSs, which were primarily based on a review of the available literature. The data from this report was an important input to other tasks that followed.

The CS characterizations included descriptions of geography, oceanography, ecosystem characteristics, fisheries activity and production in the area. It also included descriptions of the existing management procedures and overall objectives, stock assessment methods used; as well as identification of the main relevant authorities, operators and other stakeholders. The governance within the fisheries was also discussed, as well as issues related to compliance and transparency. The main findings in the evaluation of the SFPAs or the high-seas fishery was presented; and the supply-/value chains studied. The CS characterizations also included overviews of how FarFish could address the gaps and challenges identified, as well as links to the most relevant literature and data.

The case studies cover a range of fisheries of different complexity, from largely single (or a few) tuna fisheries to multi-species demersal fisheries. The management regimes do also range from essentially no management in the case of the high-seas mixed fishery in the South West Atlantic (FAO Major Fishing Area 41), to management at the national and Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) levels. While each CS is in general unique, they all face similar problems and challenges. These include overcapacity, overexploitation, threats to food security, inadequate monitoring of catches and fishing effort, lack of compliance and enforcement, inadequate data for stock assessment and for evaluating the effects of fishing (e.g. gear selectivity), lack of expertise and training in fisheries biology, stock assessment and management, lack of data and analysis for

evaluation and understanding of variability in abundance, competition between national and foreign fleets, and insufficient or inadequate value chain infrastructure.

Month 4 – Data input protocol for the FFDB

The report contains the initial data input protocol for the FarFish Database (FFDB) where much of the data collected within the project will be stored and made available for the project partners, as well as beyond the project. The first section of the report e-states and clarifies the aims of Task 6.1 (Development of the FarFish database); that it is a collection of components whose aim is to collate data from partners and integrate FarFish outputs with the FarFish website. The second part of the report details the likely nature of these components, and discusses the infrastructure and architecture required to support these tools.

Month 6 – Data Management Plan

FarFish is a part of the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot and is therefore obligated to develop and implement a Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP was initially developed in the first months of the project and was then regularly updated throughout the project lifetime. The final version of the DMP, published in the last month of the project contains 47 forms detailing the content of all datasets used within FarFish, how it will be preserved, and steps taken to make data publicly available after the project end.

Month 6 - Dissemination and exportation plan

All H2020 projects are required to develop and implement a Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR). The PEDR describes the FarFish project partners' strategies and actions for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of the project results. The plan was first published in month six of the project and was then regularly revised and updated throughout the project lifetime.

The FarFish consortium has disseminated and communicated the results and recommendations obtained from the project's work to all relevant parties, including FarFish partners, stakeholders and the general public. The use of efficient and productive internal and external communication, actions, tools and participative events has ensured that all target groups have been reached, to the extent possible. The plan described within PEDR entails how new knowledge and tools created within FarFish have been exploited and disseminated, and reports on actions taken in the project timeline including; purpose, target groups, methods, vehicles, timing, indicators and success criteria.

Month 6 – Tutor-web FarFish initial setup

The report describes the launching of the FarFish part of www.tutor-web.net making available existing teaching material directed to the target audience. The material is made available in the tutor-web as a course, under the heading "Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries." This course consists of multiple tutorials, providing material and drills at various stages of development, on topics from prerequisite mathematics, statistics and programming, through introductory fish population dynamics to methods for data-limited fisheries.

Month 7 - POPD - Requirement No. 1

This report contains detailed information on the procedures that will be implemented for collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction of data within the FarFish project and to confirm that they comply with national and EU legislation. The document does also provide detailed information on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented regarding the collection, storage and protection of personal data in the project.

The FarFish project will collect considerable amount of non-personally identifiable data as well as personal data. It is recognised by the project consortia that privacy and data security is of the utmost importance and will be given special attention. FarFish will follow national and EU regulations on data protection; in particular the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which enters into

Month 9 – Management Plan zero (MP0) for each CS

The report contains detailed descriptions of the current state of affairs in each FarFish CS. It also addresses potential improvements by suggesting CS specific objectives. The MP0 provides input to the MR invitations to be sent to the operators, after the dialogue process including authorities and operators. MP0 describes the current status in the fishery in question and is the background for the development of the Mr1 (the tailor-made good practice recommendation).

In two CSs with SFPA, where several species are targeted by different fleets, the development of a CS specific MP0 covering all the target species was considered unattainable. Consequently, the CS leaders asked to prioritize which fishery to address in the MP0 based on their challenges. Hence, the MP0s focuses on the following fisheries in the CS; mixed fishery in the South East Atlantic (FAO 47), mixed fishery in the South West Atlantic (FAO 41), the tuna fishery in Cape Verde (SFPA), the black hake fishery in Senegal (SFPA), the shrimp fishery in Mauritania (SFPA) and the tuna fishery in Seychelles (SFPA).

Month 10 - Draft 1: General guidelines for making MRs

This document contains the 1st draft of general guidelines for making management recommendations (MRs) tailored for the EU fleet operating outside European waters; in accordance with the Results-based management approach defined for the project. The RBM approach aims at delegating responsibility for fisheries management to resource users, provided that they meet with necessary requirements set forth by the competent authorities and document that they can achieve specified management objectives.

Month 11 - Executive report on stakeholder hub: attributes, tools and feedback

The report describes the state of the art of the Stakeholder's Hub in the FarFish project. Some of the main questions responded on are related to how the Stakeholder Hub has been designed and implemented, and how gaps and needs in arenas for stakeholder interaction are being matched.

This report is the first deliverable of WP1 - Stakeholder interaction. It summarises the process followed to develop the main tool for engaging stakeholders, at least on a preliminary stage. The Stakeholder Hub is focussed on a multi-level, multi-stakeholder platform, the focal point for policy-makers, NGOs, scientists, fisheries associations, processing organizations, trade companies and other relevant stakeholders.

The report provides a description of the communication flows within the first project stage about participants and stakeholders to enhance interaction between them, providing an updated list of the key stakeholders gathered to date. Finally, it describes the process of tailoring the Hub, summarizing the steps and tips followed until present time, focussing on the CS kick-off meeting planned in month 12 of the project.

Month 15 - First MP invitations submitted to case studies

This report contains the 1st management recommendation (MR) invitations submitted to the case studies in the FarFish project. The purpose of these MR invitations is to offer selected operators (resource users) the opportunity to develop MRs in accordance with the RBM approach; following the "first draft general guidelines for making MRs".

The MR invitations presented in the report are for each of the six FarFish CSs and follow up on a pre-invitation dialogues where the basics of the RBM approach have been introduced. The MR invitations include a short description of what is to be the main focus of the MRs, identification of the main actors and their roles and responsibilities in the process, details on the current status of the fishery

and finally the identification of so-called Outcome Targets (OTs) that are specific and measurable performance goals that the MRs are to meet.

It should be taken into consideration that this initial MR invitation is a preliminary version that will be developed further within the FarFish project. The OTs are for example likely to be developed further during the course of the project. It does also have to be considered that the EU fleet is only a subset of the resource users in the case studies, which is likely to have effect on the MRs in respect to impact, coverage and issues concerning “level playing field”.

Month 12 – FFDB pilot version 1

One of many products of the FarFish project is the FarFish Data Base (FFDB), which is intended to make the data collected within the various tasks within the FarFish project available for project partners in an operational way. The FFDB will be a repository for wide range of data and will allow for users to easily upload new data and make queries e.g. for input to visualisation- and decision support tools developed in other tasks in the project. The FFDB will be open access on the FarFish webpage and towards the end of the project the relevant datasets will be uploaded from FFDB to OpenAIRE; the data repository of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot.

A data input protocol for the FFDB was developed within the first four months of the FarFish project. The work on the development of the FFDB has continued since then and the core infrastructure for data collection and on-line visualisation tools is now live i.e. the FFDB pilot version 1 is available. This report presents the tools that have been built on this platform so far, which are now ready for the various work packages and case studies within the FarFish project to use. The report does as well include a discussion on the work ahead in developing the FFDB further, in particular what are the next directions for development in FFDB Pilot 2.

Month 12 - Visualisation materials and tools available for MP1 development

Development of visualisation materials and other visualisation tools that allow stakeholders to easily understand otherwise complicate data on e.g. biological, ecological, economic, social and political issues relevant for the six FarFish case studies is an important component of the FarFish project. These visualisation materials and tools have the purpose of assisting stakeholders within the case studies when developing MRs, by sowing in a simple manner historic data and forecasts. The forecasts are in particular intended to provide stakeholders with most likely scenarios or effects of MR implementation (what if? scenarios). The visualisation materials and other visualisation tools do also have an important purpose for overall aim of the FarFish project, when it comes to advancing

knowledge on fisheries in the case studies, both for internal use within the project and for stakeholders outside of the project.

The FarFish project is run in an iterative process, which amongst other things means that MRs will be developed, tested/validated and audited/valuated twice during the lifetime of the project. The first MRs (MR1) are to be developed and audited in the first half of the project, and these will then be reassessed and improved for a second version (MR2) that is to be completed towards the end of the project. The visualisation materials and other visualisation tools are also expected to go through similar iterative process, where the first versions are intended to assist stakeholders with developing MR1. This report describes the progress and current status of the visualisation materials and visualisation tools that have been, or are intended to be, made available within the FarFish project to support MR1 development. Some of the visualisation materials and tools discussed in this report are still under design, but are intended to be available for the MR1 development, as the MRs are not due until eight months after the submission of this report.

It is said that “picture is worth a thousand words” and it is important to remember that sometimes visualisation is the only way for successful dissemination of results. The visualisation materials and other tools that will be available for the MR1 development are likely to be “imperfect” given the timing within the project, but will nevertheless provide important input to developing an applicable MR1 alternatives. The tools are likely to consist mainly of static maps and charts, as well as simple GIS.

The report lists the possible visualisation materials that are and can be available within the FarFish project. Both ideas and concrete examples are listed on the use of visualisation tools for enhanced understanding and better use of the data created within the project.

Month 12 - Report on developments needed to produce relevant management tools

This report describes the developments needed to produce management tools that are relevant for each of the case studies in the FarFish project. The tools have been selected in coordination with the production of Management Plan zero for each case study. It has shared with other project partners draws on the consultation process with partners of FarFish, including the case study leaders, and with external relevant bodies such as ICCAT and IOTC. The selected tools have been incorporated into the Management Plan Zero and have also been coordinated with WP2 to feed through upcoming reports/deliverables. The tools are planned to use the data available from the FFDP and provide results that will be stored in the same database. They incorporate measures to explore better compliance through satellite advances in sensing and communication, models for semi-automatic stock assessment when needed or assessment of the role of the physical environment in

creating stock fluctuations. They have all been identified during the consultancy process as necessary and non-redundant with the tools presently available in the different case studies.

Month 12 - Report on training needs assessment

The United Nations University Fisheries Training Programme (UNU-FTP) completed a Training Needs Assessments in relation to the FarFish project in the four Case Study countries; Mauritania, Senegal, Cape Verde, and Seychelles. The primary aim of these assessments was to determine mutually agreed upon capacity building priorities to form the basis for training administered through the FarFish project. These Training Needs Assessments targeted institutions partnering in the FarFish project within the case study countries and were conducted through site visits during which key staff were interviewed by UNU-FTP team. The initial results of these assessments were presented to FarFish partners on site at the end of the field visits, and input from FarFish partners were incorporated in this final Training Needs Assessment report.

Institutional arrangement, management structure, data collection strategies, priorities, and wider fisheries development context in each case study country is unique. In Mauritania, given the importance of pelagic fisheries, the team identified the specific need to develop capacity in the field of acoustic surveys for stock assessment. Also, considering the importance of the upwelling system in total production, a closer cooperation within the IMROP department researching Oceanography and the Stock Assessment department could yield higher resolution analysis required for predictive modelling of stocks. In Senegal, the CRODT scientists are each tasked with a specific area of study but lack research support staff to successfully complete their mandate to provide scientific advice to fisheries policy makers. In this case, institutional constraints have led to an overworked and overcommitted core team of researchers who heavily rely on doctoral students to complete basic research. In the Senegalese context, there is one species allocated Total Allowable Catch (TAC), shrimp, and while other stocks are monitored through significant data collection efforts, there is no predictive modelling taking place. It was determined that stock assessment and modelling are the key priorities for building institutional capacity at CRODT. In Cape Verde, INDP has one stock assessment researcher on staff, but there is a strong determination to invest in building research capacity to conduct stock assessment. In Seychelles, the SFA is undergoing a transition towards financial autonomy, which may impact the primary mandates of the organisation. A newly established quota on yellowfin tuna in the Indian Ocean demands more predictive stock modelling methodologies of SFA scientists.

Month 14 - Report on biological and ecological data in FarFish DataBase pilot version 1

The report describes the efforts and results made on advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models in the first year of the FarFish project. The work focused on the compilation of biological, ecological and fisheries dependent and fisheries independent data that is required for other FarFish WPs. During the first year of FarFish, some modifications in the objectives occurred, resulting in changes in the species. For example, in the Cape Verde and Seychelles CSs, the focus is now on by-catch species that are not assessed by the Regional Management Fisheries Organizations (RMFO): the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC). Lists of species for each CS have now been drawn up, sources of data identified, contacts have been made with RMFOs and DG MARE, and data is being compiled. Data compilation has been largely driven by the FarFish Data Base (FFDB) template developed in WP6. On the other hand, other data required for visualization purposes, especially time series, is also being compiled or requested. A formal data request is being prepared for DG MARE, while coastal state CS participants will be requested to provide data for the FFDB. Talks are also ongoing with RFMOs, especially CECAF, regarding data acquisition and how FarFish can contribute or add value to assessment and management. Actions that need to be taken by Task 2.3 participants include the provision of data and uploading of data to the FFDB. Task 2.3 is ongoing (Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 2, due in Month 26 (July 31, 2019)).

Month 14 - Report from the MR Kick-off meetings

In line with the RBM approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in the FarFish project. Wide variety of stakeholders have been contacted throughout the first year of the project in order to contribute to the development of the MRs. The first multi-stakeholder physical meeting was held in Vigo, Spain, on the 26th -27th of June 2018. The meeting was titled “Strengthening fisheries sustainability outside EU” and was the official MR kick-off meeting. This report reports on that meeting. The aim of the meeting was to discuss stakeholders’ interests and needs, related to how they can contribute to the development of the MRs, while improving the sustainability of the fishery of the EU fleet fishing in distant waters. The current status of the work in the different FarFish working groups and case studies were presented to inform the attendants on issues like “where are we”, “what are the options” and “what do we need”.

Despite all challenges in culture, language and interest/needs, progress was made on important issues in the project. Having representatives from both EU and China, as well as authorities from countries that have signed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) with the EU around the table was one important step towards strengthening EU fisheries sustainability outside EU waters. With relevance to the high-seas case studies, representatives from both the Chinese

Academy of Fisheries Sciences (CAFS) and the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) presented their views on the high-seas fisheries. LDAC emphasized the need for a level playing field for fishing operators from EU and non-EU countries, ensuring that all fleets abide by the same international rules and regulations. CAFS highlighted the challenges and main policies that apply to the Chinese distant water fleet and want to contribute actively towards goals aiming towards a more sustainable fishery.

To ensure the best utilization of stakeholders' knowledge and contribution, the participants from similar case studies separated into two working groups. In light of the communicated interests and needs of stakeholders, potential Outcome Targets (OTs) and MRs were drafted. Defining OTs is challenging as they are to be initially defined by authorities and implemented by operators, but through the cooperation of both authorities and operators, FarFish has now succeeded in drafting OTs that most stakeholders took part in the discussions of, which in accordance to the RBM approach should ensure successful implementation of the MRs. The fruitful discussions in this meeting emphasize that this exercise can be thought provoking. WP3 and WP4 drafted potential alternative scenarios after the meeting, based on outcomes of the meeting, the MPO, and OTs presented in MR Invitations. It is however, obvious that many management strategies will achieve a given OT, when the set indicators are yes/no or present/absent. In those cases, the need for modelling of scenarios is redundant.

Month 14 - First annual report

This 1st annual report provides an overview of the overall progress in the FarFish project during its first year from the viewpoint of WP8 (Project management). The report contains details on the main meetings organised by WP8, which were the kick-off meeting in June 2017, seven Project Management Group Meetings (PMG), the first annual meeting held in Portsmouth in May 2018, the Scientific Group (SC) meeting in connection with the annual meeting in Portsmouth, and a Work package - and Case study leaders workshop meeting held in Faro, Portugal in November 2017. WP8 has also followed progress and use of resources by collecting financial and technical reports from each partner every six months. Meeting minutes, agendas, participant lists from the various meetings are compiled in this report.

The overall progress has for the most parts been as planned and all planned external, internal deliverables of FarFish have been delivered, and milestones 1, 2 and 6 were reached on time.

Month 16 - Templates and protocols for self-sampling

In the EU, the Data Collection Framework (DCF) applies to all fisheries carried out by EU vessels, including those fishing outside EU waters under Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements

(SFPA). Although observer coverage of up to 100% has been achieved through collaboration with industry in some SFPA fisheries, the observer coverage in many other SFPAs is low. Lack of data for stock assessment and management of numerous key stocks and species is a global problem. In this context, self-sampling schemes have been implemented in a wide range of commercial and recreational fisheries worldwide as a supplement to data collected by observers. Studies in the EU have shown that self-sampling can be a valuable and cost-effective method of data collection, with the added benefit of involving fishers in the scientific process of assessment and management of their fisheries. In EU fisheries, much of the self-sampling in recent years has been driven by the Common Fishery Policy (CFP) landings obligation (discards ban), where reference fleets (selected representative vessels chosen for the self-sampling scheme) apply self-sampling of catches and discards, with samples of the latter usually brought back to land for processing by fisheries scientists. Although not common, some self-sampling schemes have used fishers to collect samples for age and growth studies and even stomachs for analysis of diets.

Self-sampling schemes require volunteer fishers who are motivated and willing to carry out the extra work. Often, an incentive (e.g. financial, more days at sea, more quota) is required to guarantee fisher collaboration. Successful self-sampling programmes are based on mutual trust building between scientists and fishers, and discussion of the goals of the research, the data/sample collection methods and how the collected data/samples will be used. Data collection protocols must be followed, with clearly written instructions and forms used. Fishers need to be adequately trained in collecting data and biological samples in a consistent and standardized way and they should be provided with all the necessary material for the sampling.

Observer coverage in the FarFish case study (CS) SFPA fisheries is variable, reaching up to 100% in some fisheries, with the level of coverage depending on the RFMO, the SFPA context and the national legislation of the coastal states. Implementing self-sampling in the FarFish CSs was discussed with the industry (Spanish operators and LDAC) in a FarFish Workshop held in Vigo on 26-27 June 2018. The industry representatives at the workshop were not very positive towards implementing self-sampling in their fleets, due to the time required for sampling and occupation of freezer storage space by samples. More recently, the operators have however expressed greater willingness to participate in self-sampling, given certain incentives and conditions are met. This change of perspective has come up as part of the Management Recommendation (MR) development in the project. A key issue when exploring alternatives for development and potential implementation of self-sampling within the FarFish project is that it will actually add benefit beyond current initiatives and will not repeat work that is already being done.

Various alternatives for development of self-sampling within FarFish are currently being explored, one of which is in regard to black hake species and stock discrimination. A key scientific question that could be answered in part by self-sampling is that of the black hake species and stock discrimination. Although the black hake species can be identified morphologically, this requires training and is time

consuming if done on board. Alternatively, samples taken on board by the fishers could be frozen (or stored in ethanol) and taken back to land for analysis. Here, we propose an alternative approach, based on molecular/genetic sampling that would require minimal training, time for sampling and would not occupy storage space. At this point, no specific sampling templates or protocols are proposed as this issue should be taken up with the CS leaders and industry representatives.

Month 16 - Report on evaluation of governance structures of the cases

This report contains an evaluation of the governance structures of the EU long-distance fishing fleet in the six case studies of the FarFish project. These case studies include two high-seas fisheries and four fisheries that are based on Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) between the EU and coastal states. All of these fisheries are important for the fishing fleets of multiple EU countries or respond to the priorities of Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) and the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP). The report focuses on different aspects of both the structural and actor conditions, in particular focusing on monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) of the EU external fishing fleet. For each of the four SFPAs, we present the requirements set within the SFPAs, the legal framework and systems for MCS in the coastal state and their capacity. For the high-seas cases, we present the governing framework of the area where such is in place and the practice of managing the EU fleet. For all cases, challenges of and measures to mitigate by-catch and discard issues and IUU fishing are presented. Lastly, we summarise the main findings regarding both achievements and identified challenges for the six case studies. This report is based on available data and synthesises already existing information. It will function as input to the work in WP4 on management recommendations (MRs) and as a basis for further studies in the FarFish project of the governance structure of the EU fisheries outside Europe.

Month 18 - Report on description of value chains and input-output structure of the CS

This report provides a generalised mapping and description of the seafood value chains for the six case studies covered by FarFish. The work is based on publicly available data and has primarily been carried out as desktop analyses. One major challenge in this work has been the lack of reliable data, which in fact is a general challenge for these fisheries. The fisheries are conducted by multi-national fleets and different vessel types, ranging from artisanal fisheries to large scale industrial fisheries; and the reporting from these fleets vary a great deal. The available data from within the value chains from processing to consumption does vary considerably as well.

The six FarFish value chains are highly variable, despite having many of the same actors or flag states identified as main operators and much of the raw material is the same. The national configuration of

the value chains differs quite substantially, even though much of the seafood products end up in the EU. This is highlighted in this report as each case study value chain are described. This work will feed into other work in the FarFish project. It is to be highlighted that this report is not an in-depth value chain analysis, but merely a generalised description of the value chains. A proper value chain analysis will follow in 2021 when FarFish will publish a “Report on the value chain analysis for EU fisheries in international- and SFPA waters” (D3.9).

Month 20 – Management Recommendation 1 for each case study

This document serves as the first proposal for management recommendations (MR1) for each of the FarFish case studies. MRs are formal arrangements between a management authority and the operators in the respective case studies. It specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery.

These MR1 are developed following the “draft General Guidelines for making MRs” presented in FarFish and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation, where the outcome targets (OTs) for each case study are proposed. The proposed OTs area based on input from Management Plan Zero, input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting and additional stakeholder meetings facilitated by FarFish stakeholder interaction, and input from FarFish Work package (WP)/Case study (CS) leader meeting that took place in Mindelo (Cape Verde) in November 2018.

It is not the intention of the FarFish project to replicate measures that are already being worked on within the contexts of the SFPA agreements, national management authorities or RFMOs; but rather to address issues that can potentially support those and be therefore of added benefit to all stakeholders. FarFish has therefore been in good contact with the respective case study authorities, RFMOs and other stakeholders to decide on where it can be of greatest benefit to support ongoing measures.

This report is a collation of six “stand-alone” MRs i.e. for each of the FarFish case studies. They are all developed according to the same guidelines and are therefore with the same structure, which means that there is significant repetition between each MR.

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 29

Month 24 - Report on evaluation of current stock assessment models used in the case studies

This report contains a review the stock assessment carried out for the target species in each of the FarFish case study areas.

For the tuna fisheries, managed through the Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (ICCAT and IOTC, available data allows for a wide range stock assessment, ranging from catch and effort based Surplus Production models to the state of the art Stock Synthesis approach that can accommodate both age and size structure in the population and multiple stock sub-areas.

In the case of demersal and small pelagic species assessed at the regional level through CECAF and FAO, a more limited range of stock assessment methods and models are used, namely variations of Surplus Production models, and in some cases length-based cohort analysis and yield per recruit. There are few examples of the use of data-limited methods; the exception being the Catch at MSY (CMSY) approach developed by Martell and Froese (2013) and used by ICCAT and CECAF for some species.

The status of tuna and tuna-like species in the Atlantic shows a mixed picture. For some species, mainly by-catch species but also a target species (skipjack tuna), no formal assessment is possible due largely to lack of suitable data and/or to the characteristics of the species (skipjack tuna). Only two species (swordfish and blue shark) are considered not overfished or subject to overfishing, while half the other assessed species are considered subject to overfishing.

In the Indian Ocean, based on the same reference points used by ICCAT, bigeye tuna, skipjack, swordfish and blue shark are considered subject to overfishing. Yellowfin tuna and striped marlin are considered overfished/subject to overfishing, while blue marlin and indo-pacific sailfish are assessed as not overfished but subject to overfishing.

For the 26 demersal species/stocks assessed by CECAF/FAO, half of the 19 that could be assessed were judged to be over-exploited, while seven were considered fully exploited and only three not fully exploited. Due to insufficient data, inconclusive results were obtained for seven stocks, although additional information from fisheries and scientific surveys suggests that many are overexploited.

For the Southwest Atlantic, limited assessment is possible due to lack of RFMO and the fact that the European Union (EU) fleet accounts for a fraction of the non-EU long-distance fleets for which no data is available. For the Southeast Atlantic, lack of data has hampered stock assessment for some species. However, the South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO) has put in place a number of management measures and harvest control rules for some of the target species such as Patagonian toothfish, alfonsino, and deep-sea red crab

This review has shown that lack of suitable data for classical stock assessment methods is an underlying theme in all the case studies and that to date, there has been limited use of data-limited

models or approaches applied. For example, in the case of Mauritania and Senegal the number of demersal species/stocks (19) for which there is some kind of stock assessment is a fraction of the total number of commercial demersal species and stocks (more than 100 species/stocks). For these other data-limited or data-poor species FarFish can provide the tools to carry out stock assessment based on the DLM tools package which has minimal requirements (catch time series and life history parameters). FarFish deliverable 2.6 and the final WP2 report will identify sources of data, especially time series of fisheries independent catch per unit effort data from research surveys, that the CS partners can use to assess these species. In the case of by-catch species of pelagic fisheries (Seychelles and Cabo Verde) FarFish has actually compiled data for selected species that are not currently assessed by ICCAT or IOTC and these are used to illustrate the DLM package that has been developed. Thus, based on data that is mainly available from time series of research institute national surveys, along with life history parameters, FarFish can play an important role in showing how DLM can be used to carry out stock assessment of the many species for which there is currently no assessment, thereby contributing to improved management and sustainable exploitation.

Month 24 – Report on the Management Recommendations 1 audit

This report contains the audit of the 1st MRs. The audit aims to create a basis for improving the guidelines for making MRs, the MR invitations and the MRs developed in the next iteration of the project, through a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MR is being implemented as agreed. The role of the auditor is to evaluate whether the contract between the authority and the operator has been fulfilled, in the sense that the OTs listed in the MR have been achieved. In this first audit, the MR for each CS is audited ex-ante, focusing on measuring the results of the MR, based on the indicators set for each of the OTs. Two tasks are performed by the auditor at this stage, to conform with the provided documentation system and if data is available, and conduct a sensitivity analysis to establish a baseline for the evaluation of the performance in the second version of the MR.

Across all CSs some common challenges are identified by the auditor, such as the lack of clear identification of the complete fleet participating in the respective fisheries, as well as a clear framework to involve local and non-EU fleets that states ways to enter the RFMS and to exit it as well. It is also suggested that a protocol for conflict resolution would strengthen the MRs. Almost all the MRs have defined OTs that aim to increase pressure to all fleets to strive for a “level playing-field” in the fisheries conducted by multiple fleets in international waters. Therefore, good practice recommendations in involving other fleets is fundamental to facilitate that advantages of the RFMS process are taken. This challenge can be tackled in a common manner, finding CS with shared characteristics such as Senegal and Mauritania black hake fisheries, Cape Verde and Seychelles tuna fisheries and/or the high seas CS.

Other common issues across CSs identified by the auditor is the lack of specificity in terms of timeline for monitoring and follow up of the management actions. Also, in terms of available resources i.e. human and financial resources, to operationalize the OTs, although these topics are mentioned, they are not considered specific enough or assigned to specific actions. The auditor suggests therefore to build the documents around the OTs and the indicators performance, to facilitate the audit of the performance of the MR in the second loop.

The first stage of the audit presents a good overview of the development of MRs in the six different FarFish CS, the RFMS process is running adequately, although timing for completion of tasks has been a challenge. The MR show that a great amount of work and dialogue has taken place, as well as that ambitious but achievable objectives have been set. Common challenges were found such the importance to describe stronger initiative to promote broader participation in the RBM. Also, interesting opportunities were observed during the audit process, such as the possibility to use the capacity building programs to incentivise participation and adherence to the MRs.

All together the audit should provide a basis to improve and advance in the developed of the MRs in the next iteration of the FarFish project, enabling the operators to improve management goals and implementation strategies, tailoring management strategies to comply with policy requirements, while advancing their own objectives and making use of local knowledge and resources. Enabling responsive management with a clear documentation system and audit framework that allow for timely interventions and adaptive management.

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 30

Month 24 - University-level diploma programme in Marine Management and Innovation launched

The report describes how the FarFish project carried out the development of a university level Certificate program in Marine Management and Innovation. It is a certificate-awarding programme that was set up consisting of short courses taught by different FarFish institutions. The short-term courses are designed to further educate especially fish business operators and EU fleet representatives.

The planned programme is made up by several short-term courses and two main topics have been selected for the focus of the programme: Laws and regulations, and Value chain analysis. The first course will be run in March 2020 in Tromsø, Norway, with parallel streamed sessions in Vigo, Spain, and Reykjavik, Iceland. UiT the Arctic University of Norway is responsible for coordination and administration of the programme. The aim is to educate at least 5 students to graduation, and to provide an open access and adaptable on-line course for at least five years after project end.

Month 24 - Advanced post-graduate training program launched

Significant focus of the FarFish project is placed on education, knowledge transfer, and improving professional skills and competences of stakeholders within the case studies and beyond within the field of fisheries management. This includes education and knowledge transfer to a wide variety of stakeholders within the respective value chains, utilising different means; such as social media, e-learning, Tutor-web, a special university-level certificate program in Marine Management and Innovation and a six-month post-graduate program tailor-made for FarFish. This document reports on the setup and launching of the six-month post-graduate program, which was launched in September 2018 and will graduate at least five students before end of the FarFish project. Two students have already been graduated when this report is published and four more have been invited to join the programme in September 2019.

Month 24 - Tutor-web educational material ready

Training and capacity building are important components of the FarFish project. Among the training and capacity building tools developed in FarFish are e-learning courses that are made available at www.tutor-web.net. This document reports on the educational material that has been developed as part of FarFish for tutor-web. The material includes updates of previously existing tutor-web courses that have been tailored for FarFish, as well as new teaching materials directed at FarFish target audience. The material is made available in the tutor-web as a single course, under the heading "Methods and techniques for data-limited fisheries." It consists of multiple tutorials, providing material and drills at various stages of development, on topics from prerequisite mathematics, statistics and programming, through introductory fish population dynamics to methods for data-limited fisheries.

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 32

Month 26 - Intermediate report on Stakeholder hub implementation

This report provides an overview of the Stakeholder hub implementation in the FarFish project. FarFish aims to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters. To achieve this, one of the implementation tools is the Stakeholder Hub, a multi-level and multi-stakeholder network integrated by scientists, policymakers, resource users, NGOs and other stakeholders aimed to improve fisheries management competences throughout their participation. The Stakeholder Hub is a responsive and flexible platform that adopts the form of a regional working group for the six case studies involved into the project, but adopting the form of a high-level European platform, or even an international forum for cross-cutting issues. The design and implementation of the Stakeholder Hub, which combines

physical events and e-communication, to match-up the project to the different stakeholder agendas, is requiring a certain stakeholder analysis to respond on who, what and when stakeholders should be part of the Hub.

Over the last decades, different approaches for stakeholders' analysis have been widely discussed in the stakeholder management literature. Stakeholder analysis is considered as a relevant tool to develop innovative management approaches for fisheries management. In fact, decision-makers have been recognizing for a long time the need to understand who is being affected by the actions, choices and decisions, and who has the power to influence their aims.

The Stakeholder Hub is a vital component of the FarFish project, as stakeholder analysis must be inserted from the interaction and the creation of governance networks to obtain insights into how these networks are delivering outcomes within the project. Taking into account the RBM approach a framework for stakeholder analysis was selected, combining different theories. Therefore, the stakeholder analysis included in this report, is obtained by testing a model of *Stakeholder salience*, as the degree to which managers give priority to competing stakeholder claims, and the level of engagement, measured from qualitative and quantitative variables.

Month 26 - Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 2

This report describes the progress within FarFish in collecting and compiling biological, ecological and fisheries dependent and fisheries independent data that is required for other FarFish work packages. During the first year of FarFish, some modifications in the objectives occurred, resulting in changes in the species which the case studies focus at. For example, in the Cape Verde and Seychelles case studies, the focus is now on by-catch species that are not assessed by the Regional Management Fisheries Organizations (RMFOs) i.e. the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC). Lists of species for each case studies have been drawn up, sources of data identified, contacts have been made with RMFOs and DG MARE, and data compiled. Data compilation has been largely driven by the FarFish Data Base (FFDB) template developed in work package 6 (see deliverables D6.1 and D6.4). On the other hand, other data required for visualization purposes, especially time series, is also being compiled or requested. A formal data request was prepared for DG MARE, while coastal state case study participants were requested to provide data for the FFDB. Data from DG MARE has been received, but not in a readily useable form and therefore required treatment and preparation in order to be of use for FarFish purposes. Talks are also ongoing with RFMOs, especially CECAF, regarding data acquisition and how FarFish can contribute or add value to assessment and management. Acquisition of NANSEN cruise data has proved difficult. Numerous attempts and initiatives have been made, but to date, these have proved largely unsuccessful.

Month 26 - Draft 2 general guidelines for making MRs

This report contains the 2nd draft of general guidelines for making management recommendations (MRs) tailored for the EU fleet operating outside European waters; in accordance with the RBM approach.

These 2nd draft guidelines follow up on the 1st version, which were developed within FarFish in early stages of the project. Stakeholders representing the relevant authorities and the EU fleet, as well as any other stakeholders with vested interests in the specific fisheries have followed the 1st draft version of these guidelines in order to develop 1st version MRs for their fisheries. These MRs have now been reviewed and audited; and the feedback used to improve the guidelines. This process will now be repeated within the project, as these 2nd draft general guidelines will be tested/validated within the FarFish case studies. The aim is then to adapt a third and final version of the guidelines into a voluntary European standard (CEN Workshop Agreement) at the end of the project.

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 31

Month 26 - Second Management Recommendation invitations submitted to case studies

This document contains the 2nd management recommendation (MR) invitations submitted to the case studies in the FarFish project. The purpose of these MR invitations is to offer selected operators (resource users) the opportunity to develop MRs following the “second draft general guidelines for making MRs” presented by FarFish.

The MR invitations follow up on a pre-invitation dialogues where the basics of the RBM approach have been introduced. The MR invitations include a short description of what is to be the focus of the MRs, identification of the main actors and their roles and responsibilities in the process, details on the current status of the fishery and finally the identification of so-called Outcome Targets (OTs) that are performance goals that the MRs are to meet.

It should be taken into consideration that this is the second MR invitations developed within FarFish, as the project is designed to go through two loops (iterations) when it comes to development and testing/validation of the RFMS approach. The project has already published “1st draft general guidelines for making MRs”, “1st MR invitations submitted to CSs”, “1st MRs for each CS” and the “report on the audit of the 1st MRs for each CS”. There have been important “lessons learned” from the first iteration, which are now implemented in updated versions of the MR guidelines and the MR invitations.

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 33

Month 26 - Report on challenges and suggestions for improvements

The EU is obliged to ensure sustainable utilization of the fisheries' resources to which EU fleets have access to, both in the high seas and through bilateral agreements, based on the principles of good economic and social governance. This is mainly done through cooperation with Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) and national authorities in partnership countries to improve knowledge and management of the fisheries. Inadequate governance of these fisheries can hinder the goal of sustainable utilization of fisheries' resources, resulting in suboptimal or over-exploitation of shared and straddling fish stocks. On the other hand, limited knowledge regarding the processing and market conditions in partner coastal states has contributed to substantial criticism regarding the social and economic benefits that the international fisheries actually bring to the partners' countries. In line with the overall objective of the FarFish project to ensure sustainability and profitability in EU fisheries outside of Europe, this document will utilize the knowledge acquired across the FarFish project to develop tools to contribute to the application of a RBM for the CS fisheries. To this end, two separate analyses will be conducted based on the output from WP2, WP3 as well as the MR0 and MR1 developed in WP4. First from the evaluation of governance structures done in WP3, we identify the institutional challenges obstructing the achievement of the intended governance principles as expressed in the relevant fisheries agreements (SFPAs, bilateral and multilateral). Second, from the case study characterization and description of the value chains done in WP2 and WP3 respectively, we analyse the processing and market strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for the selected case studies. The main challenges from these analyses will be summarized in the form of road maps, which visualize the pathways towards achieving the ambitions identified through the RBM process in the FarFish project.

The six international fisheries analysed in this document face several challenges, many of which are shared across case studies. The lack of adequate data reporting and collection constitutes one of the major issues found across all cases. This issue is of particular relevance to ensure adequate management of the shared stocks. For each case, specific actions were identified as feasible pathways to improve this issue. In the fisheries managed through SFPAs, a common need was to strengthen the observer program via training for personnel or by improving or harmonising data reporting protocols. In the case of Mauritania and Senegal, black hake fisheries face the same challenge: a lack of a separate assessment of the two black hake species fished in these waters, due to the lack of proper identification. In this case, the two Coastal States could take a common approach and in collaboration train crew members and observers in the visual identification of these two species, which might result in more efficient utilisation of resources and potential cooperation among the coastal states towards overcoming this shared challenge.

Further, a lack of adequate monitoring, surveillance and control of the fisheries activities was also identified in all the cases. Insufficient human and technical resources, lack of adequate infrastructure and in some cases, the need to harmonize information systems were the main causes for the

implementing of the required monitoring protocols and inspections. For this challenge, each of the CSs have defined a set of actions. In particular, the analysis of the VMS and AIS data and, working towards their transmission from all fleets active in the areas, was identified as an important step to overcome this challenge. Furthermore, in the fisheries managed by SFPA, an improvement of the observer's program was identified also as an important step forward to improve the MCS.

In the analysis of the processing and market conditions, the most common issue identified was the lack of processing in the partner countries. In some cases, this is due to lack of installed capacity. In other cases, there are disincentives to land catches in their ports where EU ports are preferred. Furthermore, there is a generalized lack of knowledge about the value chain in the partner countries due to the lack of adequate market data to conduct more detailed evaluations that can facilitate access to these markets and improve the business environment for EU investors.

All the challenges identified above have been discussed and analysed in light of the implementation of a RBM in the six FarFish case studies. Operators and authorities' representatives have discussed in length these issues and identified feasible actions to help overcoming some of these issues. These solutions were linked to the challenges identified in this document and incorporated into a roadmap for these fisheries to follow up on the development of the strategies identified.

By utilizing the knowledge acquired across the FarFish project and by producing applicable tools, FarFish hopes to improve the conditions of these fisheries, so that they can achieve their overarching objective of sustainable utilisation of these valuable resources

This report was severely delayed and was not submitted until Month 33

Month 26 - FFDB pilot version 2

One of many products of the FarFish project is the FarFish Data Base (FFDB), which is intended to make the data collected within the various tasks within the project available for project partners in an operational way. The FFDB is a repository for wide range of data, which allows users to easily upload new data and make queries e.g. for input to visualisation- and decision support tools developed in other tasks in the project. The FFDB is at present available for project partners but will be open access on the FarFish webpage soon and towards the end of the project the relevant datasets will be uploaded from FFDB to OpenAIRE; the data repository of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot.

A data input protocol for the FFDB was developed within the first four months of the FarFish project. The work on the development of the FFDB has continued since then and the core infrastructure for data collection and on-line visualisation tools was available by the end of the first year of the project. This document describes the progress that has been made since then and the current state of the

suite of tools developed (FFDB Upload, FarFish DLMtool, FarFish DLMgui and FarFish Maps) in turn, as well as any ancillary work. The report does as well include a discussion on the work ahead in developing the FFDB further, in particular what are the next directions for the use of the FFDB and goals for the final FFDB deliverable.

Month 26 - Visualisation materials and tools available for MP2 development

Development of visualisation materials and other visualisation tools that allow stakeholders to easily understand otherwise complicate data on e.g. biological, ecological, economic, social and political issues relevant for the six FarFish case studies is an important component of the FarFish project. These visualisation materials and tools have the purpose of assisting stakeholders within the case studies when developing Management Recommendations (MRs), by sowing in a simple manner historic data and forecasts. The forecasts are in particular intended to provide stakeholders with most likely scenarios or effects of MR implementation (what if? scenarios). The visualisation materials and other visualisation tools do also have an important purpose for overall aim of the FarFish project, when it comes to advancing knowledge on fisheries in the case studies, both for internal use within the project and for stakeholders outside of the project.

The FarFish project is run in an iterative process, which amongst other things means that MRs will be developed, tested/validated and audited/valuated twice during the lifetime of the project. The second MRs (MR2) are to be developed and audited in the second half of the project. The visualisation materials and other visualisation tools are also expected to go through similar iterative process, where first and second versions are intended to assist stakeholders with developing MR1 and MR2. This report describes the progress and current status of the visualisation materials and visualisation tools that have been, or are intended to be, made available within the FarFish project to support MR2 development.

This report was delayed and was not submitted until Month 30

Month 26 - Report on DSTs used in CSs for developing MP1

This document contains a report of the Decision support tools (DSTs) used for developing management recommendations (MRs) in each of the FarFish case studies. These tools have been selected in coordination with the production of the version one of the Management Recommendations for each case study. It continues the work program outlined in an earlier deliverable, titled “Report on developments needed to produce relevant management tools” (D6.4) in collaboration with other work packages (WPs) of FarFish, mainly WP1 and WP4. The report shows the first outputs of the satellite work as support of compliance. It also describes in detail the tool

developed for assessing stock in data limited method situations, including its implementation and dissemination beyond FarFish and a formal assessment of relevance for stakeholders.

Month 26 – Second annual report

This 2nd annual report provides an overview of the overall progress in the FarFish project during its second year from the viewpoint of WP8 (Project management). The report contains details on delivery dates of deliverables and milestones i.e. if they were submitted on time and justifications if not; and if there were any deviations from the project plan regarding content. The report does also review the contribution and use of resources of each partner; and whether it is in line with what was expected in the project plan. The 1st periodic report, which covers the first 18 months of the project, is as well discussed; highlighting the most important issues that came out of the review process. Main consortium meetings are discussed. Deviations from original project plan and mitigation measures deployed are as well covered in the report, identifying what has not gone as planned and how that is being addressed by the consortium.

The report does also cover specifically each task in WP8, by listing up the purpose of each task and what has been done to meet the tasks.

Meeting minutes from PMG meetings, the 2019 annual meeting and the semi-annual WP & CS leader meeting are attached to this report in Appendices.

As the 1st reporting period review report of the external evaluators states ***the project has achieved most of its objectives and milestones for the period with relatively minor deviations.*** There are though reasons for concerns, which are detailed in this report. The consortium has deployed mitigation measures to deal with these concerns; and the project management team is confident that these will be sufficient to reach all objectives in the second half of the project.

Month 35 - Report on game theory and associated tools for improving fisheries agreements

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction of non-EU nations as well as international waters. In order to achieve this, the project places emphasis on stakeholder participation in a cocreational approach. Stakeholders in the FarFish case studies are however many and often with very different priorities, and sometimes contradictory agendas and objectives. Game theory is an approach that can be successful in studying exactly such cases. The FarFish project has therefore devoted a special task for applying game theory to produce theoretical optimal behaviours within the context of the case studies in the project. The results of

this game theory task are presented in this report, which is in the format of a journal article. The plan is to submit this manuscript to a peer-reviewed journal.

Month 36 - Report on the success of the self-sampling programme

In order to improve fisheries dependant data collection in SFPA value chains, the FarFish project explored the applicability of implementing self-sampling programmes within EU long-distance fisheries and initiated a pilot self-sampling program as “proof of concept”.

The pilot self-sampling programme was implemented on board three Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) trawlers fishing for black hake (*Merluccius poli* and *Merluccius senegalensis*) in Mauritanian waters and Senegalese national vessels (Industrial and Artisanal). Sampling protocols and kits were provided by FarFish. The data collected includes fishing locations, dates, depth, visual identification of the species, sex and length. Fin clips were taken and stored in 100% ethanol. A total of 867 samples were obtained from three SFPA trawlers belonging to OPROMAR, the fishing vessel Kanbal of the SOPERCA company in Senegal, and artisanal longline vessels from Senegal. DNA analysis was carried out at the University of Oviedo.

Self-sampling was successfully carried out for all the fleets. However, results of the DNA analysis showed that mislabelling (misidentification) of black hake species is significant and variable, with differences between vessels of the same fleet (SFPA) and between the different sampled fleets (SFPA, Senegal Industrial and Senegal Artisanal). These differences may be explained in part by the geographic area and depth of the sampling location, with higher probabilities of misidentification in areas and depths where both species co-exist and are found together in the catches.

These preliminary results, along with the results of a follow-up questionnaire to eight self-samplers from Senegal suggest that self-sampling on board SFPA vessels is viable, cost-effective and can provide valuable data for improving stock assessment and management. However, in the case of the black hakes, training of self-samplers in morphological identification is essential if reliable fisheries and biological data is to be collected by self-samplers.

Month 36 - Report on potential return of investments

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction (EEZ) of non-EU coastal states as well as in international waters / high seas. In order to achieve this, the aim of this deliverable is to identify, study and potentially recommend investment opportunities for EU operators within some of the project’s case study countries.

This report studies investment opportunities within the small pelagic fisheries in Mauritanian waters, and the associated value chains and the tuna fish pole and line fishery by the coast of the Atlantic Façade of Africa (mainly SW - Senegal), and the associated value chains. Also, a section is dedicated to investigating the specific case of investment of French capital in tuna fisheries in Seychelles in the Indian Ocean.

The analysis done for small pelagic fisheries in Mauritania was based on two decades of research and evaluation of the performance of the fisheries agreement with Mauritania (especially for the FAO and the EU for the ex-post evaluation of fishing agreement) and more particularly within the FarFish project over the last two years. Also, primary data was collected from IMROP collaborators, as well as key resource persons in relevant public bodies and institutions. Additional information was collected from processing plants owners and managers, as well as from the Pelagic Freezer-Trawler Association that includes nine large European pelagic fishing companies, some of which are operating in Mauritania.

This section concludes that although efforts have been made to improve the business environment in Mauritania, it remains more attractive for European investors to continue processing the landings of demersal fishes in Spain and small-pelagic ones in Baltic countries. Still, it is not suitable to foresee large European investment in developing the processing industry in Mauritania to handle the fish landed by EU vessels under the agreement, as this will go against the Common Fishery Policy (CFP) that promotes the maintaining of jobs in the EU based fishing industry. In that regards, a coherence of the external EU policies is sought: the development of the processing industry in Mauritania should be promoted only for the species that are not yet processed in the EU.

For the investigations into tuna fisheries, the analyses were based on interviews with relevant stakeholders, including shipowners and key personnel from public bodies and institutions both in West Africa and Europe (see Annex 3 for the list of stakeholders consulted). In addition, most of the data presented in this section was acquired from DG-Mare in a non-public dataset compiling every fishing lot from EU vessels operating within SFPAs in Senegal. A second case study in tuna fisheries in this case in the Indian Ocean, investigates the investment from the French company SAPMER to improve the land infrastructure in the Port of Victoria (Seychelles), as this would be the only notable investment by European interests in recent years for tuna fishing in Africa. These sections conclude that the fishing area where EU pole-and-line vessels are active is becoming less productive, decreasing the profitability of European flagged vessels, as well as of Senegalese flagged vessels that maintain close partnerships with Europe. As a response, they have attempted to extend their fishing grounds. Additional fishing opportunities are opening in The Gambia (whose EEZ is restricted) and other countries are expected to follow. Contrastingly, the EU sustainable partnership fisheries agreement with Senegal or Mauritania could include fewer fishing opportunities in terms of tonnage, as well as increasingly restrictive conditions for access and landings. European operators have

reacted so far by considering the switch to private regime, instead of operating under SFPA, as a preferred strategy.

Month 36 - Interactive Platform to integrate codes, visualization and data interaction tools for the CSs

The overall objective of WP6 within the FarFish project is to develop tools that provide added value, relevance and usefulness in support of management and decision making for the actors involved in each of the case studies in the project. To achieve this, the project has developed a suite of R-based tools that let users upload and analyse their own data purely through a web browser, so they can be used on any computer without installation or knowledge of the R programming language. The source code for the tools is also public and hosted on GitHub, allowing institutions to manage their own installation if required in the future.

The FarFish-DLMtool is an interactive tool where the users can incorporate their data and obtain pertinent information in return. The user guide provided in this report allows anyone to use the tool after the project ends. In addition, all parts of the project are open source, which means the code behind the tool and the tool itself will remain available for anyone to use and adapt, and thus remaining useful beyond the life of the project.

This report is structured in three parts, the first part corresponds to a technical user manual of the FarFish-DLMtool for people inside and outside FarFish, the second is an impact evaluation of the tool and the third describes its implementation for four bycatch species in FarFish case studies.

Month 38 - Third annual report

This 3rd annual report provides an overview of the overall progress in the FarFish project during its third year from the viewpoint of WP8 (Project management). The report contains details on delivery dates of deliverables and milestones i.e. if they were submitted on time and justifications if not; and if there were any deviations from the project plan regarding content. The report does also review the contribution and use of resources of each partner; and whether it is in line with what was expected in the project plan. Main consortium meetings are discussed. Deviations from original project plan and mitigation measures deployed are as well covered in the report, identifying what has not gone as planned and how that is being addressed by the consortium.

The report does also cover specifically each task in WP8, by listing up the purpose of each task and what has been done to carry out the tasks.

Meeting minutes from PMG meetings, the 2020 annual meeting and the semi-annual WP & CS leader meeting are attached to this report in Appendices.

The project progress during the third year of FarFish has been slower than planned, as deliverables have been “consistently” behind schedule. Mitigation measures have therefore been made to enable the FarFish consortium to catch up with the original time-plan. It appears now at end of the third year that these measures have been successful and that the project plan will be caught up with before end of year 2020.

Month 40 – The FarFish DataBase

One of many products of the FarFish project is the FarFish Data Base (FFDB), which is intended to make the data collected within the various tasks within the project available for project partners in an operational way. The FFDB is a repository for wide range of data, which allows users to easily upload new data and make queries e.g. for input to visualisation- and decision support tools developed in other tasks in the project. The FFDB is at present available for project partners but will be open access on the FarFish webpage soon and towards the end of the project the relevant datasets will be uploaded from FFDB to OpenAIRE; the data repository of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot.

A data input protocol for the FFDB was developed within the first four months of the FarFish project. The work on the development of the FFDB has continued since then and the core infrastructure for data collection and on-line visualisation tools was available by the end of the first year of the project. This document describes the progress that has been made since then and the current state of the suite of tools developed (FFDB Upload, FarFish DLMtool, FarFish DLMgui, FarFish SPiCtgui and FarFish Maps) in turn, as well as any ancillary work.

The report does as well include a discussion on the work ahead in developing the FFDB further and utilising it in different tasks for the reminder of the FarFish project.

Month 42 – Management Recommendations 2 for each case study

This report contains the Management Recommendations 2 (MR2) for each of the FarFish CSs. The MRs draw up on the experience from the iterations within the FarFish project. These MR2 were actually published twice, as the first version was available in month 42, but was resubmitted in M54 after addressing shortcomings identified in the second MR audit.

Month 43 - Report on the data collected on small pelagics and environmental forcing off west Africa

Fisheries of small pelagics, namely sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), chub mackerel (*Scomber colias*) and European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) in Morocco and Mauritania are extremely important from the socio-economic perspective. They account for the largest biomasses landed and contribute to the national economies through employment and exports of canned products, fish meal and fish oil, while also being a major source of protein for national consumption. Stocks of small pelagics in upwelling regions are characterised by strong variability in recruitment and abundance, with environmental drivers playing a key role. Most stock assessment approaches do not take into account environmental variability or interactions between species, in an ecosystem context. Understanding the drivers of fluctuations in the variability of small pelagics would contribute to improved management and conservation. For all the above reasons, the FarFish project is awarding significant efforts towards estimating population trends of small-pelagics provided by stock assessment models to find the link with environmental variables. The work is broken into two tasks i.e. the data collection part (WP2) and the modelling part (WP6). This document reports on the WP2 task, which includes compiling the data input for different models, like life history parameters and time series of catches, landings, effort, indices of abundance, as well as finding the sources to get different environmental variables.

This deliverable reports on the biological and fisheries data compiled for the three key small pelagic species. Time series suitable for modelling were compiled from a number of sources, national and international as well as fisheries dependent and fisheries independent (research surveys). Life history parameters (growth, weight-length relationships) were also compiled from different sources. Catch data time series are available since the 1970s, with reconstructed time series (Sea Around Us project) extending the time series back to 1950. Fishing effort data is available from the early 1990s, with shorter time series of abundance indices available from research surveys, for Morocco. Time series of fishing effort for Mauritania are however lacking.

Together with time series of environmental variables, the data compiled will feed WP6 where new approaches and models will be applied to gain a better understanding the population dynamics of the three small pelagics and contribute to improving management. WP6 will fit stock assessment models for these data. Resulting estimates will then be contrasted with different environmental variables and links found will contribute to gain a better understanding of the population dynamics for these three small pelagics. Disentangling the environmental effect over the population could also be further used to enhance management practices.

Month 46 - Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB

The third and final report on the FarFish data base (FFDB) was published in the final months of the project. Task 2.3 (Advancing biological and ecological knowledge) of WP2 in FarFish aimed to compile and make available in the FFDB, developed in WP6, data for the relevant stocks in the different Case Studies (CS). The data feeds into models and management tools that provide better understanding of the biology and ecology of the respective species and ecosystems, and will be used by other WPs (1, 3, 4, 5 & 6) for stakeholder interaction, development of management recommendations (MRs), modelling, stock assessment and for visualisation tools.

The two previous reports (D2.3 and D2.6) provided an overview of the data that was obtained and used as example data sets for the implementation of the Data Limited Methods (DLM) package and as input to the other WPs. In this report we focus on other sources of data, especially data that we were not able to obtain, namely Nansen survey and national research surveys.

The report provides a comprehensive overview of Nansen surveys and national research survey for the CSs. It is clear that a plethora of data suitable for application of Data DLM exists, especially in the form of national pelagic and demersal research surveys that are more continuous than the Nansen surveys. Acquisition of Nansen data was hindered by bureaucratic procedures and we strongly recommend a revision of the Data Policy to facilitate access to data. We also recommend that Nansen surveys should take into consideration the requirements for assessment and management of CSs and regional fisheries; lack of continuous time series of sampling makes Nansen data of limited use for assessment and management purposes.

Reluctance on the part of CS national institutes to provide national survey data for the FFDB limited the implementation of DLM. However, some example data sets were used to illustrate the possibilities of DLM and it is hoped that CS participants will bring their own national research survey data to the FarFish DLM course organized by WP7 with the collaboration of WP6 (planned for October 2021). We strongly recommend that CS partners explore the use of national survey and fisheries biology data for assessment of data limited stocks.

The report also reviews data collected by Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) observers and data collected by observers within the Data Collection Framework (DCF). It was concluded that the SFPA-observer data is of limited use for scientific advice purposes, while DCF data was much more complete and detailed, and could be useful for scientific advice. The final section provides an overview of the data available in Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMO) such as the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic tunas (ICCAT) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC).

Month 46 – Report on the Management Recommendation 2 audit

This report presents the audit of a draft version of the second Management Recommendations (MRs) in the FarFish project. This MR2 draft was updated during the last months of the project considering the second audit recommendations, hence providing a more final MR within the project's lifetime. The audit process is a fundamental step for the implementation of the Results-Based Management (RBM) approach. In RBM, the resource users are directly involved in the management and decision-making process. The relevant authorities continue defining the policy goals but delegate (partly) the responsibility for the planning and implementation of the management means to attain those goals to the resource users. The auditor, as an independent third party, should be able to assess the extent to which these goals have been met (Nielsen et al., 2017). In FarFish, the auditor is enacted by a research institute. However, this role can be taken by any organization with auditing capacity or by a joint audit committee designated by both parties.

The audit of the second MRs revealed interesting results in terms of the implementation of the key activities planned for achieving the Outcome Targets (OTs). Several challenges were also found in the implementation and performance of the MRs. Some of the most common challenges referred to coordination and collaboration with the Coastal States or the acting Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO), although when this was in place, the success of the action considerably increased. As the MR of the case study (CS) 1 for the Southwest Atlantic high seas, presented the critical challenge of not having a RFMO, the MR aimed to contribute towards addressing this challenge. The CS2 for the Southeast Atlantic, on the contrary, with a well-established RFMO faced the critical challenge of limited fishing activities in the area, which was reflected in a relatively low interest from the EU operators involved in the project. The high-seas fisheries CS1 and CS2, were subject to a more qualitative and somewhat subjective audit, due to the nature of the OTs and the indicators set for them.

The Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) CSs on the other hand, reported more specific indicators towards improving knowledge and methods about the status of the different stocks. Focus was also placed on strengthening and increasing observer program coverage, with improved reporting methods and protocols, aiming to fully implement electronic reporting systems in the Coastal State with capacity to adequately process data from e-logbooks. Operators' compliance was also targeted through data analysis of satellite signals from remote sensing systems (VMS and AIS). Finally, socio-economic targets were set in this second version of the MRs, with focus on data collection for catches, landings, processing, and trade, as well as market analysis and other socio-economic variables.

The notable advancement from the MR1 to the MR2 showed extensive work that renders important results throughout the implementation of the RBM. For example, reports on the implementation of self-sampling programs for stock assessment, not only from the EU fleet but further, as in the case of Senegal involving artisanal fleet targeting the same species. In other cases, big data analysis was

conducted, adding evidence to the value of remote sensing as a tool for transparency and support compliance in fisheries activities (Ruiz et al., 2019). Furthermore, several protocols and documents were developed, which are ready for implementation by the coastal state authorities, such as the harmonized catch data protocol in Cape Verde, and self-sampling training materials and a specific protocol to improve on-board observations in Mauritania.

However, several challenges were also found in the implementation and performance of the MRs. Challenges with data collection due to existing data sharing restrictions, timing, and delays of planned actions, with the added challenge of a world pandemic, as well as issues with participation and active collaboration in the programs, were found in several cases. More notable for the four SFPA CSs, was the clear difference in the success of the actions where adequate coordination and collaboration was in place with the Coastal States.

The second audit process was conducted to the extent that the MRs were reported at the time of the audit. The second version of the MRs presented at this stage are not final, as work is still ongoing within the project. Therefore, this second audit is an intermediate revision of progress based on available results, limiting therefore the possibility to audit results from ongoing work not yet reported. Within the RBM, the audit framework allows for intermediate audits to assess performance every updated version of the MR, where frequency can be stipulated in the RBM contract. A final audit of the MRs should be planned within RBM to allow for the evaluation of all the actions taken and finalized within the framework. However, within FarFish, the final audit will not be possible due to time constraints and contractual specifications within the EU research and innovation action framework. Nevertheless, the implementation of this second audit framework should serve as a guideline to continue the evaluation of the future versions of the MRs developed within the RBM approach until their completion.

Month 47 - Review on how EU fleet international- and SFPA water fisheries are managed and conducted

This report contains a journal manuscript analysing the development in four bilateral fisheries access agreements that the EU has made with non-member coastal states in terms of monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS). The four bilateral fisheries access agreements, today termed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) are: the agreement with Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal, and the Seychelles. The study analyses the changes in the access agreements over time and how the reforms in the CFP (in 1992, 2002 and 2013) and accompanying changes in regulations addressing the external dimension of the EU fleet, are enshrined in the fisheries access agreements. In addition, some considerations are made on how implementation challenges are reflected in the development of the agreements. The focus is on the formal development of the agreements and how new MCS requirements are introduced and operationalized. The study finds a clear strengthening in the MCS

provisions in the EU access agreements over time. The provisions generally follow the development in the CFP and accompanying implementing regulations, in some cases also preceding the enshrinement in EU regulations. At the same time, the analysis shows that even though there is a positive development in the MSC requirements in the agreements, the implementation of new requirements can be slow. The study concludes that on the one hand, this gradual and slow implementation might be a viable approach and a way for the EU to be able to implement its external fisheries policy, in particular when accompanied with capacity building initiatives and increased cooperation. On the other hand, if the MCS requirements are not implemented, and are not adjusted to the actual situation, they may end up as paper-regulations which over time will undermine the credibility of the access agreements.

Month 47 - Report on University-level certificate programme in Marine Management and Innovation

This report contains an evaluation of the university-level certificate programme in "Marine Management and Innovation" (SVF-6013) that was developed and ran as part of the FarFish project. The programme was organised by University of Tromsø (UiT – The Arctic University of Norway) and ran from 9-13th March 2020. A total of 22 students from all across the world attended the programme onsite in Tromsø, and many more watched live streaming from the lectures. The lectures were also recorded and have been available at the FarFish website since then. Throughout the week, participants were trained on topics such as international ocean governance, traceability, value and supply chains, food safety and economics. The training consisted of lectures, group work, field trips and final thesis. Among the 29 participants attending the programme, eight took the exam to be able to receive the certificate, and they all passed. The project therefore reached its goal of graduating at least five participants from the programme.

The exams, essays with self-chosen topics, contribute to the programme's academic outcome, and with the permission from the respective essay authors, FarFish has published a summary of six essays on the FarFish web page. The hope is that the essays will act as effective tools to make sure the programme has a learning impact beyond the course. Moreover, it is especially rewarding to know that one of the participants has already acknowledged major impact from taking the programme on his professional life. In a letter we received, the participant wrote about some exciting developments in his professional life, partly attributed to his participation in the FarFish programme.

The fact that the curriculum and the recorded lectures are now available enhances the impact of the programme, as these outputs will remain as tools for capacity building beyond the FarFish project.

Overall, the course evaluation revealed that most participants felt the programme taught interesting topics. Most were very satisfied with the course's overall content and quality, despite the sudden

change of circumstances related to the COVID-19 restrictions. With this feedback in mind, FarFish is satisfied with how the programme turned out and the impacts it is making. The International Fisheries programme at UiT is now under revision and we wish to integrate some of the FarFish course and experience in the new programme in 2022.

Month 50 - Policy Brief on the CFP external dimension towards 2022

The External Dimension of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) has increased its visibility in the last decades, both in relation to its coherence with the internal dimension (comprising bilateral access agreements within EEZ and the management of international waters subject to jurisdiction of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations) and its links with other EU policies such as cooperation for development, human rights, labour, health and trade issues.

As a relevant player in the development of global fisheries governance, the EU has an enhanced responsibility to promote sustainable and responsible fisheries management into the international scene, in its double role as a major fishing actor and the largest single market for marine products in the world.

The External fisheries policy ensures the EU commitment to jointly manage fish stocks outside EU waters where the EU fleet operates. It is in practice implemented by an active participation of the EU and other countries States and partners from around the globe through the United Nations system, including the Food and Agriculture Organisation the International Maritime Organisation or United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, Regional Fisheries Management Organizations and Regional Sea Conventions, as well as other international and regional bodies.

However, despite the solid theoretical foundations, internationally agreed principles and overarching goals upon which the External Dimension of the CFP is built, there are still many weaknesses and challenges that are hampering an effective implementation

This policy report summarizes the core elements of the EU's external fisheries policy, providing recommendations aimed to inform the revision process of the CFP towards 2022, while contributing to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals under Agenda 2030.

Month 50 - Report on the DSTs used in CSs for developing MR2

This report contains a description of the Decision support tools (DSTs) used for developing management recommendations (MRs) in each of the FarFish case studies. These tools have been selected in coordination with the production of the version two of the Management Recommendations for each case study. It continues the work program outlined in Deliverable 6.4 and 6.7 in collaboration with other work packages (WPs) of FarFish, mainly WP1, WP4 and WP7. The report shows the outputs of the satellite work in support of compliance. It summarizes the use of the FarFish-DLMtool developed for supporting stock assessment in data limited situations, including implementation, training applications and dissemination beyond FarFish. It also describes how some data limited methods were explored using small pelagics data from West Africa and the plan to use them to understand the effect of the environment on the population.

Month 50 - Summary report for the Workshop on “Improving management under fisheries agreements”

The relevance of the External Dimension aspects of the EU Common fisheries Policy (CFP) is permanently called into question, casting doubts on whether they are properly integrated within the CFP, evaluating their coherence with other EU policies and estimating their conformity and consistency with the international law of the sea. The relevant branches of this CFP are the so-called ‘Sustainable Fisheries Partnerships Agreements (SFPAs) which do represent one of the most pertinent manifestations of the EU’s international dimension.

The EU has an enhanced responsibility to promote sustainable and responsible fisheries management in international waters, assuming responsibilities as a contracting party to SFPAs. Those responsibilities range from the reinforcement of governance, to the creation of assessments to strengthen the weaknesses of these agreements by establishing inclusive policies with a real impact on society.

The FarFish project facilitated a web conference/workshop in June 2021 in order to facilitate multi-stakeholder discussions on the advantages, disadvantages and current challenges on the External Dimension of the CFP. The focus of the discussions was on the SFPAs as an instrument to strengthen the collaboration among EU and Coastal States. Organised by Centro Tecnológico del Mar- Fundación CETMAR and the Long Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) the event did offer a mix of panel discussions and different interventions to explore how the CFP External Dimension can be a driver for beneficial change in the field of sustainable fisheries and governance in international waters, in order to improve the implementation of the External Dimension of the CFP in the next period (2023-2033). This report contains a summary of the discussions at the workshop and main conclusions.

From a general view, the conclusions describe a relatively optimistic balance for SFPAs as contributors to sustainable fisheries. Nevertheless, there is still room to improve, especially in order to respond to the needs and interests of coastal states and local communities.

Many of the conclusions formulated during the workshop have assisted the FarFish consortium to feed into a position paper that was submitted to the EC public consultation procedure aimed to inform the revision process of the CFP towards 2022. In addition, some of these recommendations described in the report, are feeding the creation of a policy brief that will be presented at the final FarFish meeting in mid-November 2021, as a new opportunity to generate a strategic document that efficiently encompasses concrete responses and actions towards the CPF review

Month 50 - Report on the governance of European fisheries in international- and SFPA waters

This report is the third deliverable of Task 3.1 within the FarFish project, which focuses on analysing the governance of the EU external fishing fleet, that is industrial vessels over 24m LOA flagged in EU Member States operating most of its time outside EU waters. In the previous deliverable of this task, D3.10, the development of the monitoring and control of the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) providing fisheries access in other coastal states' EEZ was analysed. In this deliverable, FarFish analyses fisheries on the high seas, more precisely the fisheries taking place in the Southwest Atlantic high seas and highlights the lack of an adequate regional framework with a set of rules to effectively manage and control the fisheries taking place in this area. The deliverable is a manuscript for a scientific journal. It briefly describes the fisheries in the area and given the lack of obligations for coastal and port states, it is mainly focused on the obligations of the flag states to manage the fisheries and to cooperate to that end. Finally, it presents a number of reasons that might explain why there is not binding conservation and management measures in place on the Southwest Atlantic high seas fisheries.

Month 50 - Report on the advanced post-graduate training program

Training, education and capacity building are key objectives of FarFish. The project has addressed these objectives in variable approaches, depending on the needs of the different target groups. One of these approaches is outlined as “advanced post-graduate programme for key personnel working in reliant supply chains”. The programme was successfully delivered by the GRÓ Fisheries Training programme (GRÓ-FTP), as reported in this document. This six-month programme was adapted for FarFish partners in the Case Study SFPA countries and targeted participants in influential positions, to provide and create in-depth knowledge on fisheries management and related issues.

The GRÓ-FTP is an established training programme, based in Iceland and funded through the Ministry for Foreign Affairs as part of Iceland's Official Development Assistance. The mission of GRÓ-FTP is to enhance capacity of individuals and institutions in developing countries to sustainably use living aquatic resources. The programme began operation in 1998. The core activity of the GRÓ-FTP is an annual six-month post graduate fellowship programme, targeting mid-career fisheries professionals from developing countries. Fellowships are awarded based upon an established set of selection criteria, candidates are selected to participate in cooperation with their institutions.

A total of five (5) fellowships were awarded through the duration of the FarFish project to scientists and experts working in FarFish Case Study partner organisations. These fellowships were awarded based upon the FarFish Training Needs Assessments and subsequent visits to the Case Study countries, in which capacity gaps and priorities were established.

The post-graduate training was impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to international travel restrictions, fellows who had been selected for training in the 2020-2021 cohort were required to delay their participation by one year. As such, even with the extension of the FarFish project, the five fellows were not able to complete the programme within the life of the FarFish project. Nevertheless, three (3) FarFish fellows fully completed their studies, with research reports produced and published on the groftp.is website, and two (2) FarFish fellows are currently enrolled in the GRÓ-FTP six month programme, and are expected to graduate in March 2022.

This document outlines the selection of fellows for training, the structure of the six-month training, and summarises the outputs of the fellows' research projects.

Month 52 - WP2 final report

In the last months of the project, WP2 published a report to review the main findings, lessons learnt, and provide recommendations based on the nine deliverables produced by the WP that correspond to the five main tasks of WP2 (Advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models) of the FarFish project. For each task, a summary is provided of the main findings and lessons learnt and recommendations made, based on the deliverables corresponding to each task.

Month 52 - Report on Tutor-web training activities in FarFish

Training and capacity building are important components of the FarFish project, and one of the project's products are e-learning courses that are intended to educate stakeholders and scientist in the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment. The courses are made available at www.tutor-web.net. This report provides an overview of the e-learning component of the project,

the tutor-web tool and the training activities facilitated by FarFish to promote uptake and use of the tool. The setup and content of the FarFish material available on Tutor-web has previously been reported on in previous FarFish reports but is briefly reviewed in the report to provide insight into why this platform is important and relevant for the FarFish project.

The Tutor-web training activities as originally planned included an in-country demonstration giving short local courses in the FarFish case study countries on the use of the tool, leaving expertise on how to teach fisheries management and stock assessments using personalized educational technology. The training activities were intended to constitute a proof of concept where the FarFish experts would travel on-site to the Seychelles to demonstrate the applicability of the solution. This plan was however disrupted by Covid 19, as travel to the Seychelles (or any of the other case study countries) by the European experts was considered irresponsible and unsafe. The proof of concept was as results incorporated into the UNESCO-GRO Fisheries Training Programme, where 28 fellows from 17 countries (including representatives from all of the FarFish case studies) attended. The training demonstrated the relevance of the FarFish Tutor-web component, where the students can learn about the basics of fisheries management and stock assessment with the e-learning materials. The training activity also provided indications that the platform would be used by the fellows to become the teachers and advocates of the Tutor-web platform when returning home.

The Tutor-web task within FarFish has in addition delivered three peer-reviewed journal articles, which are briefly discussed in this report.

Month 52 - Measuring socio-economic impacts of the SFPAs through the analysis of EU Fleet (inter) connections in foreign countries

Data availability is a recurrent barrier when attempting to analyse the human dimension in fisheries. This report introduces a methodological approach to measure the human dimension within Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement fisheries (SFPAs), combining different variables which are going further from those used within the current ex-ante ex-post evaluations.

The methodological approach combines quantitative and qualitative data sources, namely literature review, data gathering and harmonization and in-depth interviews, to develop a comprehensive and accurate description of the human dimension of long-distance fisheries of the EU within the SFPAs of Cabo Verde and Senegal. The method follows a 4 steps process set to provide a better understanding of the magnitude of fishing activity: (1) environmental and fisheries; (2) human dimension at sea; (3) human dimension at port; and (4) human dimension at international level.

These case studies selected for testing the methodological approach, have displayed significant results on the importance of the fishing dimension in their national fisheries.

The analysis of Cabo Verde points out how the tuna fishery is a high-relevant activity for the EU fleet. It is prompting a development of the processing industry also driving local socioeconomic development, despite certain weaknesses in port infrastructure to support the processing industry.

In the Senegalese case study, the variety of actors, species and trade flows have mitigated the role of EU fleet as primary agent. Nevertheless, the SFPA has facilitated linkages between EU capital and local fleets through mixed-ventures.

The case studies evidence the applicability of the method and provide relevant outputs, overlooked in other analysis. Finally, the conclusion suggests next steps to advance forward the approach, particularly for those flows involving the EU and the NON-EU long-distance fleet.

Month 52 - Report on the value chain analysis for EU fisheries in international- and SFPA waters

This report contains a value chain analysis of the FarFish case studies and builds on a previously published report from the project, where the value chains were described. The report is the final deliverable for task 3.2 of the project ('Analysing the value chains of the FarFish case studies'). The original intention was to provide one draft manuscript for a peer-reviewed journal. As the covid-19 pandemic did not allow in-country case visits and with the large differences encountered between the various value chains in the identified case studies, we instead refined our research questions and instead present three draft value chain manuscripts intended for journal submission.

The first draft discusses traceability aspects of the tuna value chains of Cabo Verde and Seychelles. It presents SFPA catches by area and gear and landing place. There are economic incentives for vessels to misreport, and clear traceability challenges. The two tuna value chains are examined from a traceability perspective focusing on how information is recorded and verified. Processors have sophisticated systems and hold lots separate through production, allowing tracing of finished products to fishing vessel and date. Catch certificates are required for exports to EU, being their major markets. These have shortcomings especially related to lack of an EU-wide electronic registry.

The second draft investigates recent major changes in the value chain for small pelagics in Mauritania. Historically a major component of the EU SFPA fleet exploited sardinella that was frozen onboard and traded to countries in the Gulf of Guinea. This formed an important source of affordable but high- quality protein. However, management changes in Mauritania made this fishery less attractive and a large share of catches have been processed into fish meal and oil, thus becoming inputs into totally different value chains and no longer supplied as food to African markets.

The third draft manuscript investigates the Argentine hake fishery in the Southwest Atlantic. Here, Spanish trawlers fish in both the high seas and in national waters for hake which is primarily consumed in the Spanish market. The supply from this fishery has become increasingly important.

The fishery has management issues. It is not governed by any RFMO, the stock is at risk of overfishing, and without adequate management, is not eligible for ecolabeling. The draft discusses the supply of hake to the Spanish market, the potential implications of a supply shortfall due to reduced catches, and the need to strive for certification.

Finally, a section discussing the West-African tuna SFPAs in unison is provided. This is not intended as a journal manuscript, but for publication in a report series.

Month 52 - Policy recommendations relating to how European fleet international- and SFPA water fisheries could be managed and conducted

This report synthesises the main findings from the value chain- and governance analysis in FarFish, and point at some potential policy changes that could improve governance of the SFPAs and the high seas fisheries of the European external fishing fleet.

This is the final deliverable from work package 3 (WP3) of the FarFish project, containing lessons learned and policy recommendations based on the work conducted in *T3.1 Evaluation of governance structures* and *T3.2 Value chain analysis*. The overall objective of FarFish is to improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability. To this end, WP3 has conducted value chain analysis and evaluations of the governance structure of the EU external fishing fleet in the selected case studies. The studies have provided insights to how these fisheries are managed and conducted, and how the fisheries are utilized and are contributing to the seafood supply, including to the European market and partner countries.

This report synthesises the main findings from these studies. Based on the lessons learned as well as interaction with other areas within the project, we discuss recommendations for potential policy changes that could improve governance of the SFPAs and European high seas fisheries. The fisheries and value chains analysed are highly professional and are based on the different companies' commercial considerations. The recommendations to improve the performance of these companies or to achieve wider socio-economic goals are therefore directed at the potential for changes and improvements by way of regulations. The suggestions would in most cases require further elaboration and discussions, hence the term potential.

Month 52 - Report on “Implementing RFMS in international- and SFPA waters: lessons learned in pilot studies”

This report is the final deliverable of work package four (WP4) within the FarFish project. The WP is titled “Development of management recommendations” and has focused on developing so called Management Recommendations (MRs) within the FarFish case studies. The MR concept is based on Results-Based Management (RBM) approaches, with the aim to delegate management responsibilities to resource users. The aim of this report is to review the RBM process applied in FarFish and the lessons learned in the case studies. The report is in the format of a peer-review journal paper, which is planned to be submitted to a journal shortly.

Month 52 - Policy recommendations for improved management through the adoption of RFMS for EU vessels fishing in international- and SFPA waters

The results-based management (RBM) is a concept introduced in the Common Fisheries Policy of the European Union in 2009, to reduce micromanagement and increase the degree of co-management by transferring part of the responsibility for fisheries management to resource users. A practical framework to RBM was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan, where the RBM was conceptualized as a contract situation (Nielsen et al., 2015, 2017) where the relevant authorities set specific and measurable objectives to be achieved, leaving resource users to propose ways to achieve them and to document their achievement (Santiago et al., 2015). This approach to RBM was operationalized within six different case studies (CS) within the FarFish project, involving two EU fisheries in the high-seas, in the Southwest and Southeast Atlantic respectively, and four under Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPA) in Cape Verde, Senegal, Mauritania, and Seychelles. Relevant institutions and operators’ representatives were involved in the implementation of the RBM approach. This exercise rendered interesting results for each of the cases but also revealed shortcomings for a broader implementation of a more participatory, inclusive, and responsive approach to fisheries governance. As a pivotal factor for the success of the approach, participation was highlighted as the vertebral axis of the process. Ensuring meaningful and effective participation enabled the process to render most advancements towards improved fisheries management. Effective and meaningful engagement and collaboration were only possible when participation is managed as a priority. Absence of relevant bodies, sectors and fleet segments proved detriment throughout all cases. Also, the structured dialogue process as well as planned evaluations and iterations of the RBM contract enabled responsiveness, adaptation, and continuous improvement of the management process. Additional lessons were drawn on the importance of scoping, goal setting and timing of the actions, as well as managing realistic expectations of the goals set within the RBM. Data availability and accountability was also a major highlight, considering that

in cases where cooperation succeeded, data was made available, and knowledge therefore was expanded and enriched. The purpose of this document is to summarize the lessons learnt from the implementation of the RBM in the last four and a half years within the six case studies of the FarFish project, with the aim to propose a set of policy recommendations for the improvement of the fisheries management through the adoption of RBM for EU vessels fishing in international- and SFPAs waters.

Month 54 - Report on small-pelagics and environmental forcing off the west coast of Africa

The north west coast of Africa, particularly the Moroccan Atlantic coast is characterized by a high primary production and high derived biomass of small pelagic species. The fishery of this group plays a key role in the Moroccan fisheries sector. The recent registered increase of the fishing mortality levels during the last decades requires intervention and analyses of the fishing pressure level on the small pelagic stocks, as there are several biological signal indications of a decrease in the stock capacity under a highly dynamic hydro-climatic environment. This report aims to represent the contribution of different oceanographic variables explaining the stock abundance fluctuations. There is an overall lack of detailed biological data (length-age composition, weight, maturity, etc.) regarding fisheries in the west coast of Africa. After reviewing and collecting all available data, especially surveys data about the abundance of small pelagic populations, the stock of chub mackerel in the center and south of Moroccan Atlantic coast was selected based on the data availability. This stock dynamics was evaluated using an approach of data limited methods (Surplus Production model in Continuous Time, SPiCT model) and subsequently we explored the relationship between this model results (Relative Biomass trend) and different environmental forcing. We carried out a correlation analysis of the stock abundance trend and the environmental covariates of the study area. A strong correlation between environmental forcing and population dynamics was captured and allowed us to identify the factors that can affect the stock abundance. Among the environmental drivers studied, salinity, chlorophyll concentration, net primary production, oxygen concentration and nitrate concentration are the main variables significantly correlated with the spatio-temporal variations of chub mackerel abundance, which are the main factors that may describe the upwelling intensity and the estimated fluctuations of the relative biomass of the stock. These variables can be included in this stock assessment model or other fisheries management approaches in order to estimate the different scenarios of the stock dynamics under different environmental conditions. Our results bring crucial information due to the typical fisheries management models need to be adapted to consider both the fishery impact and the environmental effects, to produce a series of outputs on the assessment and management of exploited fish stocks. The results of this approach can be used to achieve agreement, develop and support policy advice that should be taken in response to changing

resources condition. Reaching these management measures will be a high challenge for fishery managers, but it seen as a necessary step in the long term.

Month 54 - Report on the success of in-country workshop

The FarFish in-country short course (Task 7.6) was delivered as a hybrid online/in person workshop September 29th-October 1st 2021. The course was broken into two sections, commencing with an open seminar on Data Limited Methods, and followed by a closed workshop on the use of the FarFish DLM Tool. A total of 50 participants attended the open seminar, and nine (9) attendees took part in the closed workshop that followed. The timing of the course, delivery methods, and target audience were modified in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The scope and topic for the course were selected based upon the Training Needs Assessments (TNAs) carried out the first year of the project, in combination with other meetings and discussions with project partners. It was determined through those dialogues that the course would be most beneficial and useful to a wider variety of stakeholders and partners if it were offered as a regional course, rather than an in-country course targeting only one country. It was determined through the TNAs and subsequent conversations with case study partners that the concept of data limited methods for stock assessment, and more specifically, the Data Limited Methods (DLM) Tool developed through the FarFish project would be the most useful topic for the course.

The course was originally intended to be held in Mindelo, Cabo Verde in April 2020, and was to be regional in focus, with participants nominated by their institutions. The FarFish case study partners were the original intended audience for this course, with participants hailing from the FarFish case study partner institutions, namely INDAP/IMar in Cabo Verde, ISRA/CRODT in Senegal, IMROP in Mauritania, and SFA in Seychelles.

When it became clear that travel limitations due to the COVID-19 pandemic would make an in-person regional course impossible, a new solution was developed in which a hybrid online/in-person model could be used. As it is very difficult to remotely deliver the one-on-one attention required to support learning in the workshop to practice the DLM tool, the course was broken into two sections; one open to the public providing a general overview of Data Limited Methods, and how they can be useful in stock assessment, and the second a closed, intensive workshop for fellows of the GRÓ-FTP studying stock assessment as well as scientists from the case study countries who were interested to attend, albeit remotely. The course was delivered from GRÓ-FTP's home institution, the Marine and Freshwater Research Institute in Iceland.

The seminar part of the DLM course was held on the morning of September 29, 2021, and was open to participants who registered online beforehand, as well as those attending in person through the GRÓ-FTP six-month programme. In total, 30 people were onsite for the seminar, and 20 joined via

teams. The seminar began with an introduction to another EU Horizon 2020-funded research project, EuroSea, in which the use of remote sensing via the Copernicus system was described. The seminar then included a combination of lectures and activities related to the theoretical development of data limited methods, and how they have evolved over time.

The closed part of the workshop was attended by nine (9) individuals, from eight (8) countries. Notably, these include representatives from all the original target audience of FarFish case study institutions, including Senegal, Mauritania, Cabo Verde, and Seychelles, with the addition of GRÓ-FTP stock assessment fellows, hailing from Indonesia, Papua New Guinea, Sierra Leone, and El Salvador as well. Participants from Seychelles and Cabo Verde joined the workshop online, and the others were onsite. The course was taught by Margarita Rincon (IEO, Spain) and Kamarel Ba (ISRA/CRODT, Senegal).

Month 54 - Project summary report aimed at a wider audience

The FarFish project published a so called “Legacy booklet” towards the end of the project, which is intended to summarise progress and key results to a wider audience e.g. to stakeholders that do not have scientific background or expert knowledge on the main project topics. The publication of this “project summary report aimed at a wider audience” was described in the original project description as follows:

Task 7.8 Project summary report aimed at a wider audience: In order to make the project results widely known and understood by everyone with an interest in the subject, the project coordinator will produce a project summary report at the end of the project. The report will describe in layman-terms the project as a whole, the main challenges and the most important results. This will facilitate dissemination to a wider audience, which will be important when considering the wide range of stakeholders connected to the subject.

The “Legacy booklet” is presented in this report and is also available on <https://www.farfish.eu/publications/>

Month 54 - General guidelines for making MRs published as CWA

This report describes the progress made in attempting to adopt the FarFish general guidelines for developing MRs into a CEN Workshop Agreement.

A key component of the FarFish project was the development of so-called Management Recommendations (MRs) in the project’s six case studies. The case studies included two high-seas areas and four areas where the EU has negotiated access for its long-distance fleets in Sustainable

Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs). The case studies were in the Southwest Atlantic international waters (FAO area 41), the Southeast Atlantic international waters (FAO area 47, SEAFO Convection Area), The Cape Verde SFPA fishery, the Senegal SFPA fishery, the Mauritania SFPA fishery and the Seychelles SFPA fishery.

The concept behind the approach of developing MRs was the idea that stakeholder driven, bottom-up methodologies in development and implementation of fisheries management could be more efficient than the current top-down micromanagement approaches. The concept is based on Results-Based Management (RBM) approaches and had been developed and tested in previous FP7 and H2020 projects ([EcoFishMan](#), [MareFrame](#) and [ClimeFish](#)).

To facilitate uptake and relevance of the approach beyond the FarFish project, the general guidelines for making MRs tailored for the EU fleet operating outside EU waters entered the open process of creating a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). CEN is the European Committee for Standardization. CEN Workshop Agreements are, by definition, CEN reference documents (although sometimes referred to as low-level standards). By publishing the guidelines as a CWA, the final document needs to be compliant with the rules of CEN and have gone through an open, transparent and inclusive process, as described and provided by CEN. CWAs are valid for 3 years, with possible 3-year extension if requested by committee members. The CWAs are distributed by CEN and apply to rules and regulations of CEN (including IPR rules). In most cases the CWAs remain as reference documents, but in some instances the CWA become basis for ISO standards.

The CWA process was initiated on 13 May 2020 with a public announcement on the CEN and FarFish websites, and lasted for 18 months, ending with a consensus meeting held on 25 November 2021. After 18-month CWA process that required significant efforts and diplomacy, the authors of this report must admit a defeat in trying to adopt the “Good practice guidelines for developing management recommendations for the EU fleets operating outside European waters” into a CWA. The draft CWA is available in Appendix 2 and is available for anyone that wants to explore further development or application

Month 54 – Concluding symposium

The FarFish project facilitated an international final conference in the last month of the project. The aim of the conference was to disseminate key results of the project to the external community and stakeholders interested in the subject. The conference had been planned as a physical event in Brussels but was in the end run as an online event, due to COVID. The conference consisted of 13 presentations and panel discussions, which were all translated into English, Spanish and French. The conference was attended by 128 participants from 88 companies/organisations and 30 countries.

All of the conference proceedings (in all three languages) are available on the FarFish webpage <https://www.farfish.eu/farfish-final-conference/> where it will be maintained for at least the next three years.

Month 54 – FarFish final report

This report provides an overall review of the FarFish project regarding project progress and main results. The project started in June 2017 and came to an end in November 2021. The main objective of the project was to “improve knowledge on and management of EU fisheries outside Europe, while contributing to sustainability and long-term profitability”. Looking back on what the project has delivered it is safe to say that it has made significant contributions towards its main objectives.

The report reviews the deliverables produced, which represent major project outcomes. The report also reviews important events that were used to disseminate project outcomes to important stakeholders.

4 Events

Major conferences and workshops

FarFish facilitated 8 major conferences and workshops during its lifetime, most of which are available on the project website <https://www.farfish.eu/international-conference/>. These are:

1. [Strengthening fisheries sustainability outside EU](#) held in Vigo 26-27 June 2018
2. [Bringing fisheries sustainability into the high seas](#) held in Madrid 18 September 2019
3. [Sustainable fisheries in the SW Atlantic: A scientific approach](#), held online 4 March 2021
4. CECAF and DG MARE workshop held online 19 October 2020 where FarFish key results were presented to selected group of experts at CECAF and DG MARE
5. [The external dimension of the CFP conference](#) held online 1-2 June 2021
6. [Small pelagics and climate change in the CECAF area](#) held online 29 June 2021
7. [DLM course / in-country workshop / Tutor-Web workshop](#) held as hybrid event 29 September – 29 October 2021
8. [FarFish final conference](#) held online 10 November 2021

FarFish did also take part in a number of major external events, such as the Belem Forum in Brazil held in July 2018, “our Atlantic Ocean for Growth and Well-Being” held in Cabo Verde in November 2018, and a workshop hosted by DG RTD and DG MARE on H2020 Fisheries topics held in March 2018.

Internal meetings and workshops

FarFish did also facilitate a large number of internal meetings and workshops including 10 consortium meetings (six physical and four virtual) that all partners, selected stakeholders from the Reference Group and External Expert Advisers attended. Twelve uptake meetings where CS stakeholders attended (six physical and six virtual). The Project Management Group was also very active and held 31 meetings to review progress and take important decisions on management of the project.